

Derivation of Bisphenol A HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs): BPA HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general population & BPA HBM-GV_{Worker} for occupationally exposed adults

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Glossary

ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
AF _A	Assessment Factor for interspecies differences
AF _H	Assessment Factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
AUC	Area Under the Curve
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
BfR	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPA-DG	Bisphenol A diglucuronide
BPA-G	Bisphenol A glucuronide
BPA-MG	Bisphenol A monoglucuronide
BPA-MS	Bisphenol A monosulfate
BPA-DS	Bisphenol A disulfate
BPA-S	Bisphenol A sulfate
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower confidence Limit
CEF Panel	Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids
CLP	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, and Reprotoxic
CoRAP	Community Rolling Action Plan
DFG	German Research Foundation
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level
DPHP	Di-2-propylheptyl phthalate
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ED	Endocrine Disrupting
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EHR	Enterohepatic Recirculation
ER	Estrogen Receptor

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EU	European Union
HBM-GV	HBM Guidance Value
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	HBM-GV for the general population
HBM-GV _{Worker}	HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
HEDF	Human Equivalent Dose Factor
HR	Hazard Rate
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
GI	Gastrointestinal
GM	Geometric Mean
IOELV	Indicative Occupational Exposure Limit Value
LLE	Liquid-Liquid Extraction
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
MoA	Mode of Action
NIOSH America)	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (United States of
NO(A)EC	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
PC	Polycarbonate
POD	Point of Departure
p-TDI	Provisional Tolerable Daily Intake
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride plastic polymer
REACH	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RfD	Reference dose
RIVM	Netherlands National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (European Commission)
SML	Specific Migration Limit
SPE	Solid-Phase Extraction

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SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TBE	Terminal End Bud
TSD	Toy Safety Directive (Directive 2009/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2009 on the safety of toys)
t-TDI	Temporary Tolerable Daily Intake
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value
TWA	Time Weighted Average
UGT	Uridine diphosphate and Glucuronosyltransferase
WoE	Weight of Evidence

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1 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme, HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper previously described in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (HBM4EU concept paper - publication in preparation).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 28 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission but are without prejudice to existing or ongoing risk assessment work in order to inform EU policy-making.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) are derived and discussed for Bisphenol A (BPA). No occupational HBM-GV (HBM-GV_{Worker}) is proposed considering that the high background level of BPA coming from the food intake is making the discrimination with occupational exposure difficult (when using total urinary BPA as biomarker of exposure).

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2 General information on BPA

2.1 Identification of the substance

Name	4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (bisphenol A or BPA)
IUPAC Names	4,4'-Dihydroxy-2,2-diphenylpropane; 2,2-bis(4-Hydroxyphenyl)propane ; 4-[2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)propan-2-yl]phenol
CAS Number	80-05-7
EC /List no.	201-245-8
InChI Key	IISBACLAFKSPIT-UHFFFAOYSA-N
Molecular weight	228.29 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂
Structural formula	<p>Figure 1: Structural formula of BPA (source: www.chemspider.com)</p>

2.2 Physico-chemical properties of BPA

BPA is synthesised by the condensation of phenol with acetone in the presence of a catalyst, a strongly acidic ion-exchange resin (Corrales, 2015; Geens et al, 2012). This organic phenolic compound is highly reactive due to the presence of hydroxyl groups (Almeida et al., 2018).

The purity of BPA is stated as being 99-99.8% depending upon the manufacturer. Impurities typically include phenol (<0.06%), ortho- and para- isomers of BPA (<0.2%) and water (<0.2%) (EU RAR, 2003). The proposal for a BPA restriction report (ANSES, 2014), later amended to become the background document to the RAC and SEAC opinions of Annex XV BPA restriction dossier (ECHA, 2015), indicates more widely a degree of purity of BPA superior to 80% (all percentages are in w/w). Key physico-chemical property values are presented in Table 1.

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Table 1: Physico-chemical properties of BPA

Physical state	White solid at 20°C and 101.3 kPa (flakes or crystals), mild phenolic odour under ambient conditions	O'Neil, 2006 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
		Ashford, 1994 (as cited by ECHA, 2017)
Melting point	150–158°C	Cousins et al., 2002 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
	155°C	Experimental result (Method 10294, ASTM D4493, Method 58255B) (as cited by ECHA, 2017)
Boiling point	360°C at 101.3 kPa (decomposition likely)	ECHA, 2017
Relative density	1.195 kg/dm ³ at 25°C	IUCLID, 2000 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
Vapour pressure	5.3·10 ⁻⁶ Pa at 25°C	Cousins et al., 2002 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
Partition coefficient n-octanol/water (log Kow)	3.4 at 21.5°C and pH 6.4	Experimental result (OECD Guideline 10 ; Partition Coefficient ; shake flask Method) (as mentioned by ECHA, 2017)
Water solubility	120–300 mg/L in water at 25 °C	Cousins et al., 2002 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
	381 mg/L in water at 25 °C	Li et al., 2007
	300 mg/L at 25°C	Experimental result (OECD Guideline 105 ; flask method) (as cited by ECHA, 2017)
Dissociation constant (pKa value)	9.59–11.30	Cousins et al., 2002 (as cited by EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
	11.3	Zjawiony and Pasciak, 1978 (as cited by ECHA, 2017)

At room temperature, BPA has a low vapor pressure ($3.96 \cdot 10^{-7}$ to $8.7 \cdot 10^{-10}$ mm Hg) and a high boiling point (360°C at 101.3 kPa) (Staples et al., 1998). Therefore, vapor phase exposure to BPA would not be expected at normal temperature and pressure (20°C, 100 kPa) (Hines et al., 2017a). However, experimental data on the potential for vapor formation at temperatures $\geq 100^\circ\text{C}$ are not available in the scientific literature.

2.3 Uses of BPA

BPA is a high-production volume chemical, extensively used in the industrial, commercial, consumer and domestic fields. According to current ECHA's information¹, BPA is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in 1 000 000 - 10 000 000 tonnes per year.

BPA was first synthesised in 1891, by condensation of two phenol groups and one acetone molecule. In the 1930's, screening exercises to find synthetic chemicals that could replace the natural estrogens in pharmacological applications were performed and BPA was identified at that time as a weak functional estrogen (Dodds and Lawson, 1938; Kortenkamp et al., 2016). However, it was never used as a pharmaceutical hormone, because another synthesised chemical, diethylstilbestrol, showed even more potent estrogenic properties (Dodds et al., 1938).

¹ ECHA's infocard on BPA: <https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/guest/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.001.133>

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BPA has found multiple uses since 1940, predominantly as:

- (1) monomer in the manufacturing of polymers such as polycarbonate (PC) plastics, epoxy resins, polysulfone, or polyacrylate;
- (2) antioxidant and inhibitor of end of polymerisation in polyvinyl chloride plastics (PVC);
- (3) precursor for the synthesis of the flame retardant tetrabromobisphenol-A (Geens et al., 2011).

PC plastics can be found in construction materials, electrical/electronic devices, automotive parts, some repeated use articles intended to come into contact with food and medical and healthcare devices (EFSA, 2006; EFSA, 2015). Epoxy resins are used in electrical/electronic devices and in various coatings (e.g. food and beverage can and coil coatings, marine coatings, protective coatings, powder coatings) (EFSA, 2015). For a review of all applications of PC and epoxy resins, see ANSES (2011a).

BPA is also widely used as a colour-developing agent in thermal paper, which includes a variety of uses such as cash register and credit card receipts, public transport and parking tickets, self-adhesive labels, etc (ECHA, 2014; Geens et al., 2011). The amount of BPA used in thermal paper and placed on the EU market by EU manufacturers was 2606 and 2776 tonnes in 2016 and 2017 respectively (ECHA, 2018a).

2.4 Existing EU classification and regulation on BPA

2.4.1 Harmonised classification and labelling

BPA is currently classified in the EU as reproductive toxicant Category 1B under the EU classification and labelling (CLP) Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008. Since March 2018, all manufacturers, importers, or suppliers of BPA must classify and label mixtures containing BPA as toxic for reproduction Category 1B.

Table 2: BPA classification according to Annex VI of the EU Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

International Chemical Identification	CAS No	Classification		Labelling	
		Hazard Class & Category code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
Bisphenol A; 4,4'-Isopropylidene-diphenol	80-05-7	Repr. 1B STOT SE 3 Eye Dam. 1 Skin Sens. 1	H360F - <i>may damage fertility</i> H335 - <i>may cause respiratory irritation</i> H318 - <i>causes serious eye damage</i> H317 - <i>may cause an allergic skin reaction</i>	GHS08 GHS05 GHS07 Dgr	H360F H335 H318 H317

2.4.2 EU directives and regulations of BPA

BPA is addressed under several EU Directives and regulations (ANSES, 2017):

2.4.2.1 Food contact materials

Since February 2018, Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/213 on the use of BPA in varnishes and coatings intended to come into contact with food and amending Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 as regards the use of that substance in plastic food contact materials reduces the previous specific migration limit (SML) to 0.05 mg/kg for BPA from plastic and applies the same SML to varnished

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and coated food contact materials. This new regulation, which entered into force in September 2018, also expands the ban on the use of BPA in the manufacture of PC infant feeding bottles, drinking cups or bottles intended for infants and young children.

2.4.2.2 Cosmetic products safety

BPA is part of the list of substances prohibited in cosmetic products under Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009. However, the non-intended presence of a small quantity of a prohibited substance, stemming from impurities of natural or synthetic ingredients, the manufacturing process, storage, migration from packaging, which is technically unavoidable in good manufacturing practice, shall be permitted (provided that such presence is in conformity with Article 3 with regard to the safety for human health when cosmetic products are used under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use).

2.4.2.3 Toy Safety Directive

On May 2017, the EU published a new Directive 2017/898/EC amending the Toy Safety Directive (TSD) and adopting a lower SML of 0.04 mg/L for BPA in toys which are intended for children under 3 years of age or in other toys intended to be put in the mouth (under Appendix C of Annex II to TSD 2009/48/EC). This lower SML came into force from November 2018.

2.4.2.4 Occupational safety and health

Regarding the occupational field, Commission Directive 2009/161/EU of December 2009 established an indicative occupational exposure limit (OEL) of 10 mg/m³ (8h-TWA) for inhalable dust of BPA. Furthermore, the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values (SCOEL) recommended in 2014 the value of 2 mg/m³ with respiratory tract irritation as critical effect (SCOEL, 2014).

BPA, being currently classified under CLP regulation as reprotoxic 1B, respiratory irritant and skin sensitiser, fulfils the criteria specified in Annex I.3 (a-c) of the EU Directive 94/33/EC on young people at work (applicable to any person under 18 years of age), that specifies that young people must not be in contact with this type of substance.

2.4.2.5 Restriction in thermal paper

In December 2016, the European Commission decided to restrict BPA in thermal paper in the EU (Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/2235). This ban will take effect in January 2020, giving manufacturers, importers and users of thermal paper the time to phase it out and find an alternative.

2.4.2.6 Identification as Substance of Very High Concern

In January 2017, BPA was listed in the candidate list of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHCs), due to its reprotoxic properties (ECHA, 2017a, 2017b).

In June 2017, ECHA's Member States Committee supported the French proposal to additionally identify BPA as SVHC also because of its endocrine disrupting (ED) properties, which cause probable serious effects to human health and give rise to an equivalent level of concern to carcinogenic, mutagenic, toxic to reproduction (CMRs Category 1A or 1B) substances.

Finally, in January 2018, the BPA entry was updated to reflect an additional reason for inclusion in the SVHC Candidate List due to its ED properties causing adverse effects to the environment (ECHA, 2018b), as proposed by Germany.

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2.5 Human exposure to BPA

2.5.1 Environmental and consumers exposure

Human exposure to BPA is acknowledged as widespread, at least in developed countries. Biomonitoring analysis of tissue and fluid samples revealed the presence of BPA in over 90% of the human population in Europe (Covaci et al., 2015) as well as in the US (Calafat et al., 2007) and Canada (Haines et al., 2012). An overview of total BPA urinary levels (P95) retrieved from individuals of the general population in HBM4EU participating countries, as well as free BPA urinary levels (P95) retrieved in the French general population and a mean serum BPA concentration measured in a large Swedish cohort are included for information in Annex 1.

Ingestion of contaminated food is expected to contribute by more than 90% to the general BPA environmental exposure for all age groups (Rudel et al., 2011). The dietary sources include both canned and non-canned foods categories (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Any residual BPA present in the final material or article made of PC plastics, epoxy resins or PVC has the potential to migrate into food with which it comes into contact (Geens et al., 2011). It may also be present in water following migration from PC water kettles, in drinking water due to migration from epoxy lining of water supply pipes (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012; von Goetz et al., 2017; KEMI, 2013), in air and in dust particles (Vandenberg et al., 2007; Vom Saal et al., 2014b; Konieczna et al., 2015). BPA has been found in 86% of house dust samples at levels ranging from 0.2 to 17.6 µg/g. In the urban outdoor environment, this compound has been detected in air samples at an average level of 0.51 ng/m³ associated with mild seasonal variation in BPA levels, with higher levels from autumn to winter and lower levels from winter to spring (Rudel et al., 2003; Vandenberg et al., 2007).

Further non-dietary sources include medical devices, dental sealants, thermal papers, toys and cosmetics (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015; Bernier & Vandenberg, 2017).

2.5.2 Occupational exposure

BPA has been detected in air samples from a plastics workplace (208 ng/m³) (reviewed by Vandenberg et al., 2007). In 2013 and 2014, the US National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) undertook a study to measure BPA exposure in U.S. manufacturing workers (Hines et al., 2018). Measurements of inhalable-fraction personal air sample at six US companies making BPA or BPA-based products were performed (Hines et al., 2017b) and the BPA geometric mean (GM) concentration was found to be 4 µg/m³ (max 920 µg/m³). Personal air concentrations were highest in the wax manufacturing/reclaim industry and in the job of working with molten BPA-filled wax, while lowest in the phenolic resin manufacturing industry and in the job of flaking phenolic resins. Important predictors of increased BPA air concentrations included activities expected to produce BPA-containing aerosols, such as handling sacks or bags of BPA or spilling BPA. Over two consecutive work days, each of the 78 participants provided seven urine samples. On average, workers in this NIOSH study had BPA levels in their urine approximately 70 times higher than adults in the U.S. general population (based on data from the 2013-2014 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), a representative sample of the U.S general population). As pointed by Ribeiro et al. (2017), despite the massive BPA production and consumption in European countries, very few studies have assessed the BPA occupational exposure in Europe.

The EU RAR (EC, 2008) identified the following occupational settings as of highest concern for inhalation of BPA: BPA manufacture (i.e. bagging and other filling activities) and manufacture of epoxy resins.

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A study conducted at two PC molding plants in southern Taiwan demonstrated that BPA particle emissions increased during the heating process, and that BPA particles mostly deposited in the nasal cavity (63.37%), alveolus (30.7%), and trachea-bronchus (5.93%). The distribution of BPA particulate sizes under operating conditions in this study was in a single mode distribution with a mass median aerodynamic diameter and geometric standard deviation of 0.84 μm and 1.97 μm . In one of the PC plants, airborne BPA concentrations ranged from 32.28 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 49.97 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Chao et al., 2015).

Workers in thermal paper factories - especially those working in the manufacture of coating material and operating coating machines (Heinälä et al., 2017, Ndaw et al., 2016) - and workers exposed in their workplace to paper containing BPA, are likely to be exposed through dermal contact.

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3 Toxicological profile of BPA

3.1 Toxicokinetics

Toxicokinetic studies of BPA were performed in rodents, sheep, non-human primates and humans (Doerge et al., 2010a, 2010b, 2010c; Völkel et al., 2002, 2005; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015; Gauderat et al., 2017). The overall toxicokinetic database can be considered as solid, providing internal dose metrics for neonatal-to-adult stages and for different routes of exposure. The major metabolic pathway of BPA in all the aforementioned species appears to be conjugation with glucuronic acid (Phase II metabolism) to BPA glucuronide (BPA-G). However, species- and life-stage dependent differences in the toxicokinetic profile of BPA must be considered when comparing toxicokinetic data from different species (EFSA, 2015).

In addition, the toxicokinetic behavior of BPA, i.e. its bioavailability, absorption rate and extent of the metabolism processes, is specific to the different exposure routes. This is an important factor that has to be necessarily considered when assessing the BPA exposure risks for the general population and for the occupationally exposed adults (Vandenberg et al., 2010, 2013).

Several physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models (Mielke and Gundert-Remy 2009; Teeguarden et al. 2005; Yang et al. 2015 ; Gauderat et al. 2017 ; Sharma et al., 2018 ; Karrer et al., 2018) have been developed to predict the BPA internal exposures in laboratory animals and/or humans in a route-specific manner (mostly the oral and dermal routes).

3.1.1 Toxicokinetic data in humans

3.1.1.1 Oral exposure

Absorption

After oral administration, BPA is rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. Human studies have suggested a complete absorption of a relatively low oral BPA dose, based on the urinary recovery of labelled BPA-glucuronide (EU-RAR, 2003, 2008; EFSA, CEF Panel, 2015).

Metabolism

Following ingestion, BPA is mostly absorbed, then rapidly metabolised in the gut wall (Mazur et al., 2010; Trdan Lusin et al., 2012) and the liver before reaching the systemic circulation. A toxicokinetic study on volunteers assessed the concentration time-course of d6-BPA after oral administration of d6-BPA in soup (average delivered dose of d6-BPA was 30.2 µg/kg bw) (Thayer et al., 2015). d6-BPA was rapidly and completely absorbed, with an average half-life of 0.45 h (absorption phase). The average peak concentration of 0.43 nM occurred at 1.6 h after ingestion of the soup. d6-BPA was then eliminated from serum with a terminal half-life of 5.5 h (elimination phase).

The metabolism step mainly produces BPA-glucuronide (BPA-G) (as monoglucuronide (BPA-MG) and diglucuronide (BPA-DG)), through uridine diphosphate-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT) isoforms. BPA may also be converted by sulfotransferases (SULTs) to BPA-sulfate (BPA-S) forms (as monosulfate (BPA-MS) and disulfate (BPA-DS)), especially during the neonatal period. As there is an earlier ontogeny of sulfotransferases compared with UGTs at early human developmental stages, early-life immaturity in glucuronidation capacity is likely to be compensated by sulfotransferases capacity (EFSA, 2008; Ginsberg and Rice, 2009). These BPA-conjugating enzymes are known to be polymorphic in humans (Trdan Lusin et al., 2012). Moreover, in vulnerable populations, such as in the developing fetus, growing infants and young children, expression of chemical metabolizing enzymes is immature, and even moderate exposure could lead to higher internal concentration of free BPA (Divakaran et al., 2014). The enzyme activity of

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hepatic UGTs for example is lower in newborns compared to adults. It increases with age until it reaches adult levels, which occurs between the ages of 3–6 months and 10 years depending on the UGT isoform (McCarver et al., 2002; Nachman et al., 2014).

Also, it has been suggested that the enzymatic activity of β -glucuronidases present in lysosomes and the endoplasmic reticulum of several tissues, including human liver and kidney (Sperker et al., 1997), could deconjugate BPA-G at the tissue level and especially in the placenta (Miki et al., 2002; Reed et al. 2005; Ginsberg and Rice, 2009; Muna et al., 2013). Deconjugation may also occur with BPA-S (Reed et al., 2005; Tobacman et al., 2005). This reactivation (deconjugation) of BPA-G and BPA-S may be more relevant in sensitive age groups, e.g. the fetus (fetal compartments and placenta), which would lead to higher concentrations of free BPA in fetal than in adult serum and thus potentially to increased BPA-induced effects. Ginsberg and Rice (2009) reviewed the uncertainties related to perinatal and infancy detoxification pathways and concluded that deconjugation at local tissue sites by the action of β -glucuronidase and arylsulfatase C provides a plausible mechanism for exposure to free BPA in human adults and fetuses despite rapid first-pass glucuronidation and argued for placing importance on deconjugation reactions in future risk assessments.

Distribution and excretion

BPA is rapidly distributed in all tissues and has no clear affinity for any one particular organ (ANSES, 2011, 2013, EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

The BPA-conjugates (BPA-G and BPA-S) formed in the GI and liver are delivered to the blood in humans to reach the kidney, being further excreted in the urine. The BPA-MG (which is the predominant form of BPA in the human body from 10 months on) is not able to cross membranes due to the highly hydrophilic glucuronic acid moiety covalently bound to BPA (Völkel et al., 2008). Within 24h after the administration, BPA is almost completely eliminated as glucuronide or sulphate conjugates via urine, with 84–97% of absorbed BPA excreted there within the first 5–7 hours following ingestion (Völkel et al., 2002, 2005). Estimated excretion half-life of total BPA in humans is approximately 6 hours. The formation of BPA conjugates is considered a detoxification process (Matthews et al., 2001; Snyder et al., 2000) especially as, unlike free BPA, they do not bind to the estrogen receptor (ER) and consequently do not display any estrogenic activity (Matthews et al. 2001; Shimizu et al. 2002). However, it cannot be excluded that the glucuronidated forms may have effects at ER independent sites (EFSA, 2015), and they are most probably interfering with certain physiological and metabolic pathways during windows of susceptibility in certain life stages such as during fetal development and early infancy (Andra et al., 2016)

BPA binds to plasma proteins, with the bound form representing ~95% and the free form ~5% of the total in humans (Csanady et al., 2002; Teeguarden et al. 2005). The blood:plasma ratio estimated in PK-Sim by Edginton et al., 2009 is 1.05 for free BPA, whereas it is 0.83 for BPA-G. The plasma protein binding fraction is 3.5% for free BPA and 95% for BPA-G (Edginton et al., 2009). In controlled human oral dosing studies using labelled BPA, free BPA (also called aglycone or unconjugated BPA) represented only 0.2–1.2 % of the total Area Under the Curve (AUC) of BPA in blood or < 2 % of the total maximum concentration (C_{max}) (Taylor et al., 2011; Völkel et al., 2002, 2005, 2008). The absolute bioavailability of BPA circulating as the aglycone form is <0.1-0.2% (Teeguarden et al., 2011).

To estimate the recovery of an oral dose of BPA, Völkel et al. (2002) administered 5 mg (60–80 μ g/kg) of d_{16} -BPA to six healthy adult volunteers (3 males, 3 females – see Table 3) in hard gelatine capsules and quantified the free and the glucuronidated BPA in blood and urine samples that were collected at 6 h intervals, for up to 96 h. The oral dose was completely recovered as d_{16} -BPA-G in urine within 24–34 h ($118 \pm 21\%$; $t_{1/2} = 5.4$ h), after d_{16} -BPA-G was rapidly cleared from

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the blood ($t_{1/2} = 5.3$ h). No free BPA was detected in either blood (limit of detection (LOD) of 10 nM (2.3 ng/ml)) or urine (LOD of 6 nM (1.4 ng/ml)).

The same authors conducted another study on volunteers, during which 25 μg (0.35–0.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) of d_{16} -BPA in 50 ml drinking water were administered to 6 healthy adult volunteers (3 males, 3 females – see Table 3) (Völkel et al., 2005). Urine samples were collected at 0, 1, 3, 5, and 7 h, and determination of total BPA was performed after hydrolysis of BPA-G, so that the total of deconjugated plus initially free BPA was detected in the analysis. Of the amount eliminated within 5 h, deconjugated plus free BPA accounted for 84% and 97% of the administered dose in women and men, respectively. Again, no free d_{16} -BPA was detected in urine; whereas the glucuronidated metabolite could be quantified in amounts corresponding to near-complete recovery of the oral dose. Thus, single oral dose intake would completely eliminate in 6–8 h and never reach steady state even with daily dosing. No blood samples were analysed in this latter study.

The results of both of the above studies are summarised in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Recovery rate of deuterated-BPA in urine of volunteers, from an orally absorbed dose

Species	Study description	Excretion rate	References
Human	Six healthy adult volunteers (3 males, 3 females), orally exposed to 60–80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ d_{16} -BPA, in gelatine capsules <i>*free BPA was not found in urine</i>	100% was excreted in urine within 96 h (urinary $t_{1/2} = 5.4$ h)	Völkel et al., 2002
Human	Six healthy adult volunteers (3 males, 3 females), orally exposed to 0.35–0.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ d_{16} -BPA, in drinking water <i>*low levels of free BPA were found in urine of 2 of the subjects, accounting for 2% of administered dose</i>	84%-97% of free BPA + BPA-G was excreted in urine within 5 h (urinary $t_{1/2} = 4$ h)	Völkel et al., 2005

No free BPA was detected in the plasma and urine samples of the study conducted by Völkel et al. in 2002, while, as reviewed by Vandenberg et al. (2007, 2010) several studies have reported levels of free BPA in serum in the low ng per ml range. Some authors speculate that this may be explained by a less sensitive analytical method applied by Völkel et al. (2002), and/or the use of hard gelatine capsules for administering BPA, which does not reflect BPA exposure via food as it prevents possible uptake of BPA by absorption through the buccal mucosa (Søeborg et al. 2014). Bypass of hepato-intestinal metabolism was hypothesised to occur in humans through absorption in the oral cavity. However, a study by Teeguarden et al. (2015) points out that this bypass seems not to occur in humans ingesting either liquid or solid foods as shown by Thayer et al. (2015b).

In support of the results by Völkel et al., 2002 and 2008 (a study in which free BPA was detected in only 10% of 474 samples from 287 subjects, in a range from <LOD (0.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) to 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$), Teeguarden et al. (2013) published a comprehensive review of robust methods for measuring or calculating BPA serum concentrations based on 93 published pharmacokinetic/toxicokinetic- and biomonitoring studies. The authors thereby concluded that serum free BPA concentrations are lower than levels measurable by analytical methods available at that time. Teeguarden et al. (2016) again concluded that recent studies increased the confidence that highest typical daily aggregate BPA exposures (~0.27 mg/kg/day), under conditions of oral, or worst-case mixed oral-dermal exposures, are producing levels of free BPA in serum in the non-pregnant adult populations that are at low pM levels (below current levels of detection). Based on this, they concluded that serum free BPA concentrations had to be much lower than total BPA levels reported and that high measurable free BPA in human serum would thus be questionable and potentially suggest contamination with BPA during handling and analysis of the samples.

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On the other hand, studies not evaluating/not measuring free BPA levels, i.e. the bioavailable form of BPA that may reach and interact with susceptible receptors in the body, are of limited value because this information is crucial for risk assessment (Soeborg et al., 2014).

In addition to urine, serum and blood, BPA has also been measured in hair (Tzatzarakis et al., 2015, Karzi et al., 2018), maternal and fetal plasma (Ikezuki et al., 2002), amniotic fluid (Ikezuki et al., 2002; Edlow et al., 2012), placental tissue (Schönfelder et al., 2002) and in the human lactating milk (Sun et al., 2004; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). Ex vivo and in vivo experiments have shown that BPA freely diffuses across the human placenta (Balakrishnan et al., 2010). Recently, Shekhar et al. (2017) investigated the association between maternal exposure to BPA and *in utero* fetal exposure levels, to gain insight into the BPA transfer from the maternal to fetal unit indicating prenatal exposure. Analysis by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) of maternal blood and amniotic fluid samples collected from 40 pregnant women at full term indicate total BPA levels of 7.43 ng/mL in maternal blood plasma and 7.75 ng/mL in the amniotic fluid. A very low positive correlation ($r = 0.343$, $p < 0.05$) was found between free BPA measured in maternal blood plasma and amniotic fluid.

Csanády et al. (2002) suggested results showing a disproportionate affinity of BPA to fat in comparison to other tissues such as kidney, muscle, and other sites. However, the EFSA CEF Panel considered that this was inconsistent with the results of well-controlled animal studies showing no toxicologically relevant accumulation in fat tissue, even though the concentration of unconjugated BPA is somewhat higher in fat compared to serum (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

The study of Genuis et al. (2011) concluded that BPA was excreted in sweat with concentrations retrieved as much as 70% higher than in serum (experience on 20 participants). The EFSA CEF Panel however considered these results as highly improbable, these high concentrations in sweat being reported in subjects without a measurable concentration in serum: yet, sweat in humans is produced as an ultrafiltrate of the blood (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

3.1.1.2 Inhalation exposure

As noted by the CEF Panel from EFSA (2015), the SCOEL (2014) or by ANSES (2011), there are essentially no data available on the toxicokinetics of BPA following inhalation exposure. However, it is assumed that appreciable absorption would occur. In the case of inhalation, BPA enters directly the blood stream from the alveoli and the lack of first pass metabolism results in bioavailability differences up to 6 times compared to a similar dose administered orally (Sarigiannis and Karakitsios, 2011). In vitro studies indicate also that first-pass metabolism of BPA does not occur in lungs (Mazur et al., 2010; Trdan Lusin et al., 2012), resulting in higher levels of free BPA after inhalation than after oral dosing.

No comparative data on the levels of free BPA after inhalation exposure are available, but a significant portion of inhaled BPA aerosols may actually become ingested (SCOEL, 2014). On the other hand, the maximum BPA concentration (C_{max}) in the liver is likely to be lower after inhalation (or dermal exposure) than after oral exposure (SCOEL, 2014).

3.1.1.3 Dermal exposure

For the dermal route, source-specific exposure levels need to be distinguished, because the absorption fractions can differ by source matrix/formulation (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Karrer et al. (2018), who re-adjusted the PBPK model for peroral exposure to BPA developed by Yang et al. (2015) and extended it to include dermal exposure, summarised the uptake parameters used in different exposure assessments of BPA: 100% for peroral exposure (EU RAR, 2008), 20% for dermal exposure from thermal paper (Toner et al., 2016), and 60% for exposure *via* personal care products (PCPs) (Biedermann et al., 2010). This value of 60% for BPA dissolved in ethanol is

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chosen, as PCPs can also contain ingredients enhancing skin penetration. As dermal absorption half-lives, 6h for thermal paper (Demierre et al., 2012) and 10 min for PCPs (Biedermann et al., 2010) were selected. As uptake periods, 15 min for peroral exposure (Tsukioka et al., 2004; Völkel et al., 2002) and 24h for dermal exposure are used, representing exposures after which BPA is not washed off for a long time, so that it can penetrate the stratum corneum, where it is protected from removal (Demierre et al., 2012). These uptake parameters are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Source-specific dermal uptake parameters used in most PBPK models and exposure assessments, according to Karrer et al. (2018)

Parameter	Dermal (thermal paper)	Dermal (PCPs)
Absorption fraction (%)	20 (Toner et al., 2016)	60 (Biedermann et al., 2010)
Absorption half-life (h)	6 (Demierre et al., 2012)	0.167 (Biedermann et al., 2010)
Uptake period (h)	24 (Demierre et al., 2012)	24 (Demierre et al., 2012)

Note: PBPK=physiologically based pharmacokinetic; PCPs=personal care products; TP=thermal paper.

BPA absorbed by dermal contact enters directly the systemic circulation, without undergoing first pass metabolism. Serum ratios of unconjugated BPA/total BPA are higher than for the oral route (increased bioavailability) and the clearance of BPA happens at a slower rate as well (Mielke et al. 2011). Indeed, the excretion half-life of BPA after dermal exposure is estimated to approximately 8h. A steady state would be attained in blood by the 4th day of exposure (Mielke et al., 2011; Mielke and Gundert-Remy, 2012; Gundert-Remy et al., 2013).

According to EFSA's assessment from 2015, available experimental evidence indicates a 24-h percutaneous penetration of BPA across human skin of 2.3–8.6%. In a study by Demierre et al. (2012) for example, defrosted (non-viable) human skins (dermatomed to 200 µm) from two donors were investigated in a flow-through cell system (applied BPA dose of 1.16 µg (applied concentration 194 ml/l with water as vehicle). After 24 h incubation, the absorbed BPA dose was 8.6% of the applied dose.

Marquet et al. (2011) have found that unmodified BPA accounted for more than 97% of the radioactivity found in the receptor fluid for both rat and human viable skins, suggesting that BPA was not metabolised during its skin transfer. They also showed that a dermal exposure of ¹⁴C-BPA results in a longer urinary half-life than i.v. exposure.

According to Thayer et al. (2015a), controlled human dermal exposure to 100 mg/kg bw d6-BPA for 12 hours leads to total urinary excretion of 0.5-3.8% of the applied dose and produces free BPA/total BPA serum AUC percentages of 11-15% (which are similar to the analogous serum percentages produced by i.v. injection in non-human primates (Doerge et al., 2010b; Patterson et al., 2013)).

Toner et al. (2018) investigated the percutaneous absorption of BPA through skin in a human *in vitro* study according to OECD TG 428, as part of a substance evaluation process (the Community rolling action plan or CoRAP) requested by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). In order to investigate potential dermal BPA metabolism during absorption, radiolabelled BPA was applied to fresh, metabolically competent, human skin samples (tested concentrations of ring-labelled ¹⁴C-BPA were 2.4, 12, 60 and 300 mg.L⁻¹). The mean absorbed dose (receptor compartment) ranged from 1.7–3.6% of the applied doses. The dermal delivery (epidermis + dermis + receptor compartment), i.e.the bioavailable dose, was 16–20% of the applied doses with the majority of the radioactivity associated with the epidermis compared to dermis and receptor fluid. No metabolism was observed in any of the epidermis samples; however, some metabolism was observed in

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dermis and receptor fluid samples with formation of BPA-G and BPA-S, and some polar metabolites.

For exposure scenarios with dermal contact to thermal paper, the EFSA CEF Panel (2015) used a conservative value of 10% dermal absorption and did not consider any skin metabolism (conservative decision). Much higher percutaneous penetration percentages are mentioned in some studies, as e.g. by Zalko et al. (2011), but severe shortcomings for some of these studies were observed (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Several studies exploring the exposure through handling of BPA-containing receipts have been performed in the last years: Lee et al. (2018) estimated the contribution of receipt handling to the body burden of BPA: 54 female cashiers were asked not to wear gloves during the work for one week, and in the following week, to wear gloves. Urine samples were collected at pre-shift and post-shift for the first two consecutive days in each week, and urinary BPA concentrations were measured. In cashiers without gloves, about a two-fold increase in urinary BPA concentrations was observed after work-shift. Lv et al. (2017) recruited 6 male volunteers required to simulate cashier's work and handle thermal receipts. Their findings show that urinary BPA concentrations were 3 times higher compared to those before the experimental period. The BPA exposure via dermal contact accounted for an estimated $70.9\% \pm 12.2\%$ (GM) of the urinary BPA retrieved (assuming that if BPA entered human body via dermal penetration, 100% of it would circulate in blood and would be excreted through urine). Ndaw et al. (2016) evaluated the exposure to BPA in 90 cashiers and in 44 non-occupationally exposed workers. The median urinary total BPA concentration was $8.92 \mu\text{g/L}$ ($6.76 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) for cashiers compared to $3.54 \mu\text{g/L}$ ($2.89 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) for the controls. However, no significant increase was observed in urinary free BPA concentrations. Some other studies however, as e.g. Porras et al., 2014 or Thayer et al., 2015c showed no evidence that repeated handling of BPA containing receipts by cashiers significantly increases total daily exposure (total daily intake). Also, Hormann et al., 2014 showed that handling of BPA receipts using dry hands in a laboratory setting did not result in exposures sufficient to increase serum total BPA concentrations; the only statistically significant change was a reduction in serum conjugated-BPA in women. However, this same study showed that if hand sanitizer containing dermal penetration enhancers was used prior to holding a thermal paper for 45 seconds, a large amount of BPA was transferred to the skin (the maximum amount of BPA that was swiped from the palm and finger). After holding the receipt for 2 seconds, 40% of the maximum was recovered. In both men and women, there was a significant increase in serum free BPA after using the hand sanitizer and then holding the thermal receipt paper and eating French fries with the BPA-contaminated hand. The combination of dermal and oral BPA absorption led to a rapid average maximum increase (C_{max}) in free BPA of $\sim 7 \text{ ng/mL}$ in serum and $\sim 20 \mu\text{g}$ total BPA/g creatinine in urine within 90 min (Hormann et al., 2014).

Biedermann et al. (2010) reported that when taking hold of a receipt consisting of thermal printing paper for 5 s, the BPA transferred to the forefinger and the middle finger could be 10 times higher when these fingers were wet or very greasy compared to rather dry finger's skin.

Thus, as reported by RIVM from the Arcadis report (2013), the estimated dermal BPA exposure due to contact with thermal paper can vary markedly depending on the % w/w BPA in thermal paper, contact area, contact time, frequency of contact and duration of handling per day, as well as with the quantity of BPA transferred from the paper to the skin, the percentage of uptake (dermal flux or absorption %) and with skin factors (dry, humid, wet or creamed skin or recently washed with detergent or alcohol) (RIVM, 2015).

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3.1.2 Toxicokinetics in animals

3.1.2.1 Absorption

The analysis of total (unconjugated and conjugated) BPA plasma concentration-time profiles after oral and IV administration in terms of the AUC suggests a degree of absorption from the GI tract up to 85-86% in rats and monkeys (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

3.1.2.2 Metabolism

For all species investigated, BPA is rapidly glucuronidated (i.e. conjugated) after absorption (Völkel et al., 2002; Yang & Fisher, 2014) and regardless of route; BPA is rapidly cleared from blood. In rodents, sulfate conjugates of BPA have also been measured (ANSES, 2011, 2013; Poet and Hays, 2018). However, while glucuronic acid conjugation is the major pathway in rodents, the aglycone is not exclusively unchanged BPA, but part of it is hydroxylated BPA (Zalko et al., 2003). Several other metabolites have also been identified, such as BPA diglucuronide, or methoxylated conjugates (Zalko et al., 2003; ANSES, 2011; Andra et al., 2016).

The BPA metabolism enzymes also differ between animals and humans (ANSES, 2011). In rats, the 2B1 isoform of UGT (UGT2B1) is mainly responsible for BPA glucuronidation (Yokota et al., 1999). In humans, UGT2B15 and 2B7 are mainly responsible for this glucuronide conjugation (Hanioka et al., 2008).

In adult rhesus monkeys, the concentration–time profile after oral administration of BPA is similar to humans, considering a similar dose as observed by Doerge et al. (2010b). Also, in this study, minimal pharmacokinetic differences were observed between neonatal and adult monkeys for the free form of BPA, which is present in less than 1% of the total circulating concentration of BPA (Doerge et al., 2010b).

In rats, fetal exposure to unconjugated BPA changes over the duration of pregnancy, based on the apparent development of Phase II metabolic capacity in the fetus: in early pregnancy the concentration of unconjugated BPA in fetal tissue is up to three times higher than in the dams, whereas later the concentration is about the same (Doerge et al., 2011a; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). Mice and rats appeared to have a similar developmental trajectory for BPA metabolic capacity over the neonatal period (Draganov et al., 2015)

3.1.2.3 Distribution and excretion

In rodents, the highest concentrations are found in the liver and the kidneys a few hours after oral administration of radiolabelled BPA (ANSES, 2011).

In rodents, the BPA-conjugates are partly eliminated *via* biliary secretion into the intestinal tract (the remaining being eliminated in the urine), where they are cleaved to release BPA which then undergoes enterohepatic recirculation (Pottenger et al., 2000; Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). The absence of enterohepatic circulation of BPA-G in humans is most likely due to a higher threshold for biliary elimination as compared to rats (Soeborg et al., 2014).

In rats, this enterohepatic circulation results in a slow excretion and prolonged low-level systemic availability of unconjugated BPA, which is supported by the observation of urinary excretion of unconjugated BPA as an appreciable fraction (1–4%) of the administered oral dose. Due to biliary secretion and enterohepatic recirculation, the predominant way of elimination of systemically available unconjugated and conjugated BPA in rodents is the fecal excretion of unconjugated BPA (> 50% of the orally absorbed BPA dose is recovered in feces) (Doerge et al., 2010a, 2011a). In contrast, monkeys, as humans, eliminate the systemically available BPA forms primarily *via* urinary excretion of BPA-conjugates.

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Overall the animal data indicate that the systemic bioavailability of unconjugated BPA by the oral route varies between the species, being 0.45% in adult mice, 0.9% in adult monkeys and 2.8% in adult rats, based on oral versus intravenous (i.v.) toxicokinetic data (Doerge et al., 2010a, b, 2011a, b, 2012; Fisher et al., 2011).

Studies of BPA toxicokinetics in fetal sheep and rhesus monkey have shown that fetal phase II metabolism leads to the production of conjugates, mainly BPA-G, which accumulate in the fetal circulation owing to their limited placental permeability (Vom Saal et al., 2014a; Corbel et al., 2013; Patterson et al., 2013; Viguié et al., 2013). A fetal sheep model developed by Gauderat et al. (2016) recently suggested that the slow elimination of BPA-G through back conversion into BPA was resulting in a gradual re-entry of BPA into fetal blood. This observation indicates that BPA-G cannot be considered simply as an inactive irreversible terminal metabolite and underlines the need to characterise human fetal exposure not only in terms of static internal exposure to BPA and BPA-G but also in dynamic terms to capture the back and forth exchanges between the BPA and BPA-G pools (Gauderat et al., 2017).

Conclusion

Some major differences between humans and rodents are observed after BPA exposure, in terms of toxicokinetics. In addition, the BPA biotransformation pathways are different in nature and proportions according to species (ANSES, 2011).

3.2 Health effects of BPA

3.2.1 Information from epidemiological studies

More than 100 epidemiology studies suggest associations between BPA exposures and a range of conditions and diseases, including metabolic syndrome, infertility, and severity of asthma (Rochester, 2013). However, most of these human epidemiological data have methodological weaknesses, which is limiting the scope of their conclusions (ANSES, 2013). The studies are generally cross-sectional in their design, which makes their interpretation regarding the causal nature of the link between the measured exposures to BPA and the observed health events (e.g. systematic account of potential confounding factors, small population size, etc.) difficult. Latest risk assessments on BPA (e.g. by EFSA CEF Panel (2015) or ANSES (2013)) rely mainly on toxicological animal data but make use of epidemiological data as supporting evidence for the critical effect selection.

Longitudinal/prospective-type studies done with increased sample sizes and in a variety of human populations would be needed to create a stronger link between BPA exposure and human health outcomes. But building a case for causal relationships between BPA and human disease is hindered especially because exposures are so ubiquitous and because decade-long longitudinal studies adequately measuring developmental exposures would be needed to recapitulate what has been experimentally tested (and observed) in laboratory animals (Vandenberg et al., 2016).

For the occupational field, information stemming from studies having evaluated the effects of BPA occupational exposure is almost negligible. Changes in male reproductive health in several functional domains (sexual function, hormone levels, and semen quality) were reported for workers in Chinese factories making BPA or BPA-based epoxy resins in a large health study (Li et al., 2010a, 2010b, 2011; Zhou et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2015). However, this study was cross-sectional and its findings have not been confirmed in a similarly exposed population (Hines et al., 2018).

Still, available studies are indicating alterations in hormone levels for both male and female workers, which is in agreement with the ED properties of BPA (Ribeiro et al., 2017).

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3.2.2 Effects on reproduction and development

BPA possesses the ability to interact with ERs which play a very important role in specific life periods, particularly in pregnant and breastfeeding women. Correspondingly, BPA is reported to have clinical effects including ovarian and uterine dysfunction in females and sexual dysfunction in males (ANSES, 2011; Caporossi & Papaleo, 2015; Almeida et al., 2018).

Strong evidence exists for the effects on the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovary axis. Animal studies have indeed revealed alterations in cerebral sexual differentiation, increased pulsatility of gonadotropin-releasing hormone and precocious puberty.

BPA is therefore an acknowledged reproductive toxicant. The basis of the CLP classification of BPA as Reprotoxic substance 1B - H360F adopted by RAC (ECHA, 2014) were the multi-generation studies by Tyl et al., 2008, 2002 (description in Annex 2), NTP, 1985 and Ema et al., 2001 and a subchronic study by Delclos et al., 2014.

RAC's opinion (ECHA, 2014) was based on adverse effects, such as disturbances in the oestrous cycle, at a dose of 600 mg/kg bw/day (Tyl et al., 2008) and at a dose of 100 mg/kg bw/day (Delclos et al., 2014). The ovarian toxicity reported in Tyl et al. (2002) included reduced absolute and relative ovarian weight at the two highest doses of 50 and 500 mg/kg bw/day and in Delclos et al. (2014) an increase in ovarian follicular cysts was observed at 300 mg/kg bw/day. In Delclos et al. (2014), an increase in cystic endometrial hyperplasia was observed in the uterus at the highest dose of 300 mg/kg bw/day.

The EFSA CEF Panel (2015) however considers that evidence for changes in reproductive function arising from in *utero* exposure of animals to lower dose of BPA (below 3.6 mg/kg bw/day) remains contradictory and highly variable between studies. Moreover, in several multi-generation studies, no effects were observed at dose levels as low as 3 µg/kg bw/day up to at least 50 mg/kg bw/day. RAC also assessed the uncertainty of the results from studies reporting reproductive effects below dose levels of 50 mg/kg bw/day as large, due to inconsistency in the study results, low reproducibility of studies indicating reproductive effects at lower doses and the uncertain adversity of the effects reported (ECHA, 2014).

Using a WoE approach, the EFSA CEF Panel assigned a likelihood level of “as likely as not” to reproductive and developmental effects of BPA at low doses (below 3.6 mg/kg bw/day). This endpoint was not taken forward for assessing the toxicological reference point, but was taken into account in the evaluation of uncertainty for hazard characterisation and risk characterisation (ECHA, 2014).

3.2.3 Effects on the mammary gland

In 2015, the EFSA CEF Panel concluded that BPA-induced effects on the mammary gland of rats, mice and monkeys exposed pre- or perinatally were “likely” effects, but considered none of the available studies on the mammary gland effects to be sufficiently robust in terms of methodology for identifying a consistent dose-response (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

In the BPA restriction dossier on thermal paper (ANSES, 2014), ANSES considered that the effects of BPA on the mammary gland were “recognised” effects in animals and had therefore to be taken into account to assess the risk to human health. Critical effects considered were ductal hyperplasia and effects on the architecture of the mammary gland, including effects on Terminal End Buds (TEB). Proposed critical doses were an oral NOAEL of 25 µg/kg bw/day and a LOAEL of 250 µg/kg bw/day for effects on these undifferentiated epithelial structures based on Moral et al. (2008).

In its opinion of June 2015, RAC concludes that BPA causes an acceleration of mammary gland maturation in experimental animals, with slight indications of relevant intraductal hyperplasia from 2 studies with subcutaneous exposure (Murray et al., 2007 and Vandenberg et al., 2008). However,

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in line with the EFSA CEF Panel (2015), no individual study was considered robust enough to serve as critical study for the identification of a starting point for DNEL derivation.

According to ECHA's support document for the identification of BPA as SVHC, various effects on the mammary gland were observed, depending on the period of exposure (ECHA, 2017). These effects include: modifications in the mammary tissue such as an increased number of TEBs relative to the ductal area, fewer apoptotic TEB cells, increased lateral branching and ductal hyperplasia, increased cell proliferation and decreased apoptosis in the glandular epithelium, ductal (and occasionally lobuloalveolar) and intraductal hyperplasia - ultimately increasing its susceptibility to chemical carcinogens.

These effects were observed in rodents or in non-human primates following prenatal and/or post-natal exposure to BPA. Available data also support the plausibility that BPA, through interaction with the nuclear ERs or G-protein-coupled ER and indirectly with the progesterone receptor, modulates estrogen and progestin agonist activities. Emerging epigenetic studies have suggested changes related to estrogen-dependent genes, as well as HOX genes (involved in embryogenesis and post-natal development), which could be associated with BPA induced abnormal development and increased cancer susceptibility of the mammary gland (ECHA, 2017).

3.2.4 Effects on brain and behaviour

Despite numerous studies over the years, available studies are not enough to draw conclusions about exposure to BPA and its neurobehavioral effects, as stated by EFSA (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Prospective studies in humans indicate that prenatal BPA exposure (BPA exposure during pregnancy) may be associated with altered child behaviour in a sex dependent manner. However, the associations are not consistent across the studies and do not provide sufficient evidence to infer a causal link between BPA exposure during pregnancy or childhood and neurodevelopmental effects in humans.

Some studies also report changes that may indicate effects of BPA on brain development (effect on neurogenesis and on gene expression, neuroendocrine effects, effects on the morphology of certain brain regions, etc.). However, whether such changes are mechanistically related to the neurobehavioral responses reported following exposure is not clear, due to inconsistent results between studies.

Some animal studies are reporting significant impairment of either learning and/or memory capacities; others are reporting effects on social behaviour and sensory-motor function. However, the results from different studies are inconsistent and controversially discussed (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012). Moreover, methodological shortcomings (e.g. small sample size, lack of consideration of the litter effect, not properly controlled variability of exposure through diet and inadequate statistics) were noted (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Using a WoE approach, EFSA assigned a likelihood level of "as likely as not" to neurological, neurodevelopmental and neuroendocrine effects of BPA. This endpoint was not taken forward for assessing the toxicological reference point, but was taken into account in the evaluation of uncertainty for hazard characterisation and risk characterisation.

RAC considered it however prudent to take the observed effects on brain and behaviour into account for hazard and risk assessment. RAC considered that the results of the study conducted in mice by Xu et al. (2010) suggest that developmental exposure to BPA can interfere with learning and memory capacities in different learning tasks in rodents, including spatial learning and passive avoidance learning together with down-regulation of the NMDA receptors. However, the effects of

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BPA on learning and memory abilities of laboratory rodents are not fully consistent, as both positive and negative effects are reported in different studies (ECHA, 2015).

More recently, a random effects meta-analysis about prenatal exposure to BPA and hyperactivity showed that early BPA exposure in humans was associated with hyperactivity in boys and girls, and in animals with significantly increased hyperactivity in male rodents (Rochester et al., 2018).

3.2.5 Effects on the metabolism

EFSA reviewed human studies on metabolic effects from which 2 were prospective while 22 were cross-sectional and thus not suitable on their own to study exposure-disease associations (EFSA, CEF Panel, 2015). A causal link between BPA exposure and metabolic effects in humans cannot be established.

A number of studies in pre- and postnatally exposed rats and mice indicate that BPA exposure could have an effect on metabolic function as evidenced by effects on glucose or insulin regulation or lipogenesis, and body weight gain. As noted by EFSA however, these studies are short-term studies and based on the results from other studies with a longer duration (e.g. 90 days) there is no convincing evidence that BPA is obesogenic after intrauterine exposure.

Using a WoE approach, the EFSA CEF Panel assigned a likelihood level of “as likely as not” to metabolic effects of BPA. This endpoint was not taken forward for assessing the toxicological reference point, but was taken into account in the evaluation of uncertainty for hazard characterisation and risk characterisation.

ANSES considered in the restriction dossier (ANSES, 2014) that the effects of BPA on metabolism were considered as critical effects to be used for the risk assessment. The study from Miyawaki et al., 2007 was selected as the key study for this type of effect and a LOAEL of 260 µg/kg bw/day was derived based on the results reported by the authors. This LOAEL is below the NOAEL used by EFSA CEF Panel and RAC in 2015 to derive a safe level with BPA. Recently published studies assessed for this dossier also reported effects of BPA at doses equivalent or below the LOAEL from Miyawaki et al. (2007). In some studies, *in vivo* and *in vitro*, non monotonic dose response relationship have been reported, which may complicate the determination of a safe level for this endpoint (García-Arévalo et al., 2016; Angle et al., 2013; Song et al., 2012). The level of sensitivity also depends on the window of exposure and the susceptibility of the exposed population and it is therefore difficult to define a safe level regarding this endpoint, with a sufficient level of confidence (ECHA, 2017).

3.2.6 Effects on the cardiovascular system

Using a WoE approach, the EFSA CEF Panel (2015) assigned a likelihood level of “as likely as not” to cardiovascular effects of BPA and thus this endpoint was not taken forward for risk characterisation. An association between exposure to BPA and cardiovascular effects is observed in epidemiological studies, but it cannot be ruled out if diet or other concurrent exposure factors were confounders. This association therefore does not provide sufficient evidence to infer a causal link between BPA exposure and cardiovascular effects in humans. A very limited number of animal studies is available for this endpoint.

3.2.7 Effects on the immune system

Based on an assessment of recent studies, the EFSA CEF Panel indicates that BPA exposure may be linked to immunological outcomes in humans. However, a causal link between BPA exposure during pregnancy or in childhood and immune effects in humans cannot be established.

Several animal studies lend support to the possibility of immunological effects of BPA, however most of these studies suffer from shortcomings in experimental design and reporting. Although

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dose-responses could not be confidently established in most studies, a dose-related effect was observed for allergic lung inflammation (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

Using a WoE approach, the EFSA CEF Panel assigned a likelihood level of “as likely as not” to “likely” to immunotoxic effects of BPA. This endpoint was not taken forward for assessing the toxicological reference point, but was taken into account in the evaluation of uncertainty for hazard characterisation and risk characterisation.

However, emerging evidence of effects of BPA on the immune function raises concern on possible effects at low doses (5 µg/kg and possibly 0.5 µg/kg in Ménard et al., 2014a and 2014b) (ECHA, 2017; RIVM, 2016). The results suggest that BPA exposure can lead to the development of food allergies and has adverse effects on resistance to infection at lower doses than anticipated by the current Toxicity Reference Values (TRVs) recommended in Europe. Neonates, infants and young children, who are exposed through their mothers during pregnancy and through breast-feeding, but also via medical devices, packaged food and the handling of products that are not intended as toys would be particularly susceptible to such immunological effects of BPA exposure (RIVM, 2016).

3.2.8 Endocrine disrupting properties

BPA has been shown to affect reproductive function, mammary gland development, cognitive function and metabolism through pathways that commonly involve disruption of estrogenic regulation. The complexity of the toxic response to BPA suggests multiple modes of action (MoA) that may interact, but most importantly, the available evidence shows that disruption of the estrogenic pathway is central and consistently involved in each of the four effects. This selection of effects is however not intended to be an exhaustive list of ED-mediated effects of BPA. The level of evidence of an ED-mediated MoA for other effects, e.g. immunotoxic effects or cardiovascular effects, are considered insufficient at this point, but it is likely that the range of effects related to the ED-properties of BPA may be wider than those mentioned before (ANSES, 2017; ECHA, 2017; Pouzaud et al., 2018; Beausoleil et al., 2018).

4 Existing toxicity reference values for BPA

Risk assessments on BPA were conducted by national agencies e.g. the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES, 2011, 2013), the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM, 2016), also EU bodies e.g. EFSA (EFSA, 2006, 2008; EFSA CEF Panel, 2010, 2011, 2015, 2016), ECHA (ECHA, 2015), as well as by international bodies such as FAO/WHO (2011), Health Canada (2008a and b) and US FDA (2014).

4.1 For the general population

Table 5 summarises existing TRVs for BPA, as e.g. intake limits, derived from recognised agencies in their respective health and risk assessments. Some assessments did not derive an intake limit per se, but did make hazard/risk decisions. The derivation of the most recent values set by both the EFSA CEF Panel (2015) and by ECHA (2015) is more thoroughly described below.

Table 5: Overview of existing toxicity reference values for BPA derived for the general population

Agency	Key study	Endpoint	Point of departure (µg/kg bw/d)	Assessment factors	TRV
EFSA CEF Panel, 2015	Tyl et al., 2008 (2-generation mouse toxicity study)	Increased relative mean kidney weight	BMDL10 8960 (HED=609 with HEDF=0.068)	150 - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 6 for the uncertainty in the database	t-TDI 4 µg/kg bw/d
ECHA, 2015	Tyl et al., 2008 (2-generation mouse toxicity study)	Increased relative mean kidney weight	BMDL10 8960 (HED=609 with HEDF=0.068)	150 - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 6 for the uncertainty in the database	oral DNEL 4 µg/kg bw/d
			BMDL10 8960 (HED=6.64 or HED=6.24 with conversion factors 'oral mouse' to 'dermal human' either 1350.4 or 1436.9 depending upon PBPK model (Yang et al., 2013 or Mielke and Gundert-Remy, 2009))	150 - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 6 for the uncertainty in the database	DNEL for dermally absorbed total BPA dose 0.1 µg/kg bw/d (with biotransformation rate of 50%)

Agency	Key study	Endpoint	Point of departure (µg/kg bw/d)	Assessment factors	TRV
Health Canada, 2008a	Tyl et al., 2002 (3-generation rat study) and Tyl et al., 2008 (2-generation mouse study)	Body weight reduction, (dev/repro effects)	LOAEL 25,000	1000 - 10 for subchronic to chronic extrapolation - 10 for interspecies differences - 10 for inter-individual differences	p-TDI 25 µg/kg bw/d
US EPA, 1993	NTP, 1982 (2-years cancer study in both rats and mice)	Reduced body weight	LOAEL 50,000	1000 - 10 for LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation - 10 for interspecies differences - 10 for inter-individual differences	RfD 50 µg/kg bw/d

DNEL = Derived No Effect Level; t-TDI = temporary Tolerable Daily Intake; RfD = reference dose; p-TDI = provisional Tolerable Daily Intake

4.1.1 EFSA

In 2015, the EFSA BPA risk assessment (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015) estimated the degree of likelihood² for the effects under consideration, on the basis of available human and animal evidence at that time. The considered “likely” effects of BPA (increase of liver and kidney weight and mammary gland proliferation) were brought forward for dose-response analysis and for defining the reference point for the temporary Tolerable Daily Intake (t-TDI) value. The effects classified as “as likely as not” (reproductive/developmental, neurological/neurobehavioural/neuroendocrine, immune, cardiovascular, carcinogenic and metabolic effects) were considered in the uncertainty analysis and were taken into account in the definition of an uncertainty extra-factor. The mean F0 relative kidney weight increase in the 2-generation study in mice by Tyl et al. (2008) was used as key endpoint.

In this study, animals (28 per sex/group) received BPA in the diet at concentrations of 0, 0.018, 0.18, 1.8, 30, 300, or 3500 ppm (equivalent to 0, 0.003, 0.03, 0.3, 5, 50, or 600 mg BPA/kg bw/day). The only systemic effects in the F0-generation were observed in males: centrilobular hepatocyte hypertrophy at ≥ 300 ppm (50 mg/kg bw/day); reduced body weight, increased kidney and liver weights, centrilobular hepatocyte hypertrophy, and renal nephropathy at ≥ 3500 ppm (600 mg/kg bw/day). There were no effects on fertility reported. Only at the highest exposure dose, developmental effects were observed, i.e. reduced F1/F2-generation weanling body weight, reduced weanling spleen and testes weights (with seminiferous tubule hypoplasia), slightly delayed preputial separation, and increased incidence of undescended testes (only in weanlings, which did not result in adverse effects on adult reproductive structures or functions), and increased gestational length by 0.3 days in F1/F2-generations. EFSA concluded that alteration in kidney weight was the most critical effect because other effects were only observed at higher doses. Based on the results of this study, a Benchmark Dose 10% Lower Confidence Limit (BMDL₁₀) of 8.96 mg/kg bw/day was calculated. This dose in mice was extrapolated to an oral Human Equivalent Dose (HED), thanks to a solid base of toxicokinetic data in various laboratory animal

² The WoE approach referred specifically to hazard identification, i.e. the likelihood of an association between BPA exposure at any dose and the effect under consideration and not to the likelihood or frequency of the effect actually occurring in humans.

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species providing internal dose metrics for neonatal-to-adult stages and for different routes of exposure and availability of PBPK models predicting internal exposures in laboratory animals and humans in a route-specific manner. Considering the interspecies variability related to the effects of BPA, chemical-specific data were used to derive the ratio between $AUC_{\text{animal}}/AUC_{\text{human}}$, i.e. the Human Equivalent Dose Factor (HEDF). This HEDF is defined by a common relationship between the external dose given to an animal and the resultant AUC of serum free BPA concentration, and the external dose given to a human and its AUC of serum free BPA concentration. The AUC_{animal} values were obtained from toxicokinetic experiments with oral administration, IV injection or subcutaneous injection in adult CD-1 mouse (also from Sprague-Dawley rats and rhesus monkeys) (Doerge et al., 2010a, b, 2011a, b, 2012). The AUC_{human} values for oral dosing of human adults were predicted by PBPK modelling using a monkey-based PBPK model (Yang et al. 2013).

The HED value of 609 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day was then obtained by multiplying the mice $BMDL_{10}$ by the HEDF of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice (given by the ratio of the AUC in mice to the AUC in humans). The t-TDI of 4 μg BPA/kg bw/day was finally obtained by dividing the HED by an overall assessment factor (AF) of 150 to account for intra-species differences (factor of 10), inter-species toxicodynamic differences (factor of 2.5) and for remaining uncertainties about possible toxic effects below the dose at which effects on the kidney are observed i.e. regarding mammary gland, reproductive, neurobehavioural, immune, and metabolic systems (extra factor of 6). The default AF of 4 for interspecies kinetic differences was already accounted for by the use of the chemical-specific approach, in which the ratio of AUC in mice to the AUC in humans was used to adjust the external doses in animals to the external doses in humans.

In 2015, EFSA's experts committed to re-evaluate the substance's toxicity when the results of newly performed studies by the US Consortium Linking Academic and Regulatory Insights on BPA Toxicity (CLARITY-BPA project)³ become available. A new working group started collecting scientific papers and data (including the report of the CLARITY-BPA 2-years core study on rodents and publications of academic studies developed from the CLARITY study) in 2018. The new assessment should be ready by 2020.

4.1.2 ECHA

In ECHA's BPA restriction dossier (ECHA, 2015), RAC agrees to use the HED approach in the risk assessment for BPA as performed by EFSA CEF Panel (2015) and also supports the EFSA value of 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day as a DNEL for oral exposure in the general public.

Based on PBPK model-based predictions of the AUC for unconjugated BPA in serum in adults for an oral dose of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw and for a dermally absorbed dose of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015) conversion factors from oral mouse doses to dermal human doses were calculated⁴. The HED approach was then applied as described in the previous section. Considering a study showing a biotransformation of a minimum 27% of the BPA dose administered in the skin (Zalko et al., 2011) and also estimating that this biotransformation rate of BPA in the skin could be higher *in vivo*, a correction taking into account a biotransformation rate of 50% was applied to derive a DNEL value of 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day for the dermally absorbed total BPA dose.

³ The CLARITY-BPA project was developed in the USA by the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and run by the National Toxicology Program (NTP).

⁴ Information of *in vitro* studies on cutaneous penetration can be used in PBPK modelling to simulate the fate of BPA taken up dermally. EFSA did this by using the Yang et al. 2013 model (for oral exposure; used for species to species extrapolation) and the Mielke et al. 2009 model (for dermal exposure, enabling predictions of serum concentration time profiles and estimations of internal dose metrics for unconjugated BPA by dermal route).

4.1.3 ANSES

In 2013, ANSES conducted a human health risk assessment for BPA taking into account the various documented sources and media of exposure. The assessment included exposure through food, by dermal contact or by inhalation, for the free and the conjugated BPA. The characterisation of the human health risks was conducted for the pregnant women and their offspring. Four toxicological endpoints were considered (neurobehavioural development, female reproductive system, metabolism and obesity and mammary gland proliferation - changes in the structure that make it more susceptible to carcinogens). The associated external threshold doses identified in oral studies conducted in developing animals and the derived toxicological values for each effect are summarised in Table 6.

Table 6: Critical effects, studies and endpoints selected in the ANSES 2013 risk assessment on BPA, associated with the derived internal toxicological values for BPA (ANSES, 2013).

Critical effects	Study reference	Species	Window of exposure	Route of exposure	LOAEL (µg/kg/d)	NOAEL * (µg/kg/d)	Internal NOAEL with bioavailability factor of 3% (µg/kg/d)	Internal toxicological value with global AF of 300 (µg/kg/d)
Brain and behaviour	Xu et al., 2010	Mice ICR	GD7-PND12	Oral	-	50	1.5	0.005
Female reproductive system	Rubin et al., 2001	Rat Sprague-Dawley	GD6-weaning	Oral	-	100	3	0.01
Metabolism and obesity	Miyawaki et al., 2007	Mice ICR	GD10-PND30	Oral	260	87	2.6	0.009
Mammary gland	Mora et al., 2008	Rat Sprague-Dawley	GD10-GD21	Oral	-	25	0.75	0.0025

* adjusted NOAEL calculated from the LOAEL

A bioavailability factor of 3% was used to convert the external NOAEL/LOAEL from the experimental data (oral administration) into equivalent internal doses (internal NOAEL/LOAEL) taking into account the impact of first-pass metabolism on orally ingested BPA and assuming that only the unconjugated fraction of BPA was responsible for the effects observed.

An overall AF of 300 was also applied to the internal NOAELs (or 900 if the starting critical dose was a LOAEL), consisting of a factor 100 to account for inter- and intraspecies kinetic and dynamic differences and an extra factor of 3 to account for uncertainties regarding possible low-dose effects of BPA and non-monotonic dose-response relationships. The resulting internal toxicological values that were used in risk characterisation were 0.005, 0.01, 0.009 and 0.0025 µg/kg bw/d BPA for respectively neural, female reproductive, metabolic and mammary gland effects.

4.1.4 Other organisations

In 2016, the Dutch RIVM published scientific publications on the developmental effects of BPA exposure on the immune system that were not taken into account by the EFSA and the RAC.

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RIVM concluded that for pre- or perinatal exposure to BPA, a LOAEL of 5 µg/kg bw/day can be derived for effects on the immune system, possibly resulting in increased risk of food intolerance, inflammation and infections in the offspring. Following the approach as used by EFSA in 2015 to derive the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d, the RIVM concludes that these effects are observed in test animals at a HED that may be more than a factor of 10 lower than the HED on which EFSA based its t-TDI. These new data would thus warrant a reconsideration of the current t-TDI. RIVM furthermore concluded that these effects are also possible at 0.5 µg/kg bw/day, but noted that the studies supporting these conclusions have limitations and that a more detailed weight of evidence analysis of the underlying data is needed to determine whether effects at this lower dose level should be considered adverse.

In their 2012 risk assessment regarding exposure and risks for the health of pregnant women likely to be exposed to different suspected ED substances, the Danish EPA used an internal DNEL of 500 µg BPA/kg bw/d to assess the health risk for pregnant women. This DNEL was obtained by application of an overall AF of 100 to the NOAEL of 50 mg/kg/day based on the estrogenic effects observed in the 2-generation study by Tyl et al., 2008 (Danish EPA, 2012). However, the Danish EPA also calculated an alternative lower DNEL, considering that reproductive effects of BPA have been found at lower doses than the effects shown in the study by Tyl et al. (2008). From the studies by Durando et al. (2007) and Murray et al. (2007) (both using subcutaneous administration of BPA to pregnant Wistar rats) a LOAEL of 25 µg/kg bw/day was identified, resulting in an alternative lower DNEL of 0.083 µg/kg bw/day (AFs of 300). Although this alternative DNEL based on low-dose effects is not used in the quantitative risk assessment, it is used for perspectivation of the obtained results (Danish EPA, 2012).

In 2012, the Swedish Institute of Environmental Medicine was commissioned by the Swedish Chemicals Agency (KEMI) to evaluate the scientific literature investigating the effects of BPA exposure during early development on developmental neurotoxicity, as well as developmental effects on the mammary gland and female reproductive system and on lipogenesis. Alternative reference doses were calculated from the selected NOAELs/LOAELs, presented in Table 7 (KEMI, 2012). KEMI thereby concluded that although no single study reviewed was considered reliable enough to alone serve as a key study for the derivation of an alternative reference dose, effects were consistently observed at doses well below those that served as the basis for the TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/day set at that time (EFSA, 2006), but also the current t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

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Table 7: Summary of identified points of departure for the derivation of an alternative reference dose for BPA in the report by the Swedish Chemicals Agency (table reproduced from KEMI, 2012)

Reference	Exposure	Animal mode	Endpoint	NOAEL (µg/kg bw/d)	LOAEL (µg/kg bw/d)	Assessment factor	Reference dose (µg/kg bw/d)
Indirect exposure of offspring via oral administration to pregnant and lactating females							
Ryan and Vandenberg, 2006	Oral to pregnant and lactating females	Mouse (C57/Bl-6) Female offspring only	Increased anxiety	2	200	175 (7 x 2.5 x 10)	0.01
Xu et al., 2010	Oral to pregnant and lactating females	Mouse (ICR) Male offspring only	Impaired spatial memory	50	500	175 (7 x 2.5 x 10)	0.29
Betancourt et al., 2010 Moral et al., 2008	Oral to pregnant females	Rat (Sprague-Dawley)	Morphological changes in the mammary gland, increased susceptibility to tumorigenesis	25	250	100 (4 x 2.5 x 10)	0.25
Jenkins et al., 2009	Oral to lactating females	Rat (Sprague-Dawley)	Morphological changes in the mammary gland, increased susceptibility to tumorigenesis	25	250	100 (4 x 2.5 x 10)	0.25
Tharp et al., 2012	Oral to pregnant females	Rhesus monkey	Morphological changes and accelerated development of the mammary gland	-	400	500 (10 x 2 x 2.5 x 10)	0.8
Somm et al., 2009	Oral to pregnant and lactating females	Rat (Sprague-Dawley)	Increased bw and adipose tissue weight, adipocyte hypertrophy, overexpression of genes	-	70	1000 (10 x 4 x 2.5 x 10)	0.07
Wei et al., 2011	Oral to pregnant and lactating females	Rat (Wistar)	obesity, dyslipidemia on a high fat diet	-	50	1000 (10 x 4 x 2.5 x 10)	0.05

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Reference	Exposure	Animal mode	Endpoint	NOAEL (µg/kg bw/d)	LOAEL (µg/kg bw/d)	Assessment factor	Reference dose (µg/kg bw/d)
Direct oral exposure in offspring							
Carr et al., 2003	Oral to offspring on PND 1- 14	Rat (Fischer 344)	Impaired spatial learning in females	100	250	100 (4 x 2.5 x 10)	1
Viberg et al., 2011	Oral to offspring on PND 10	Mouse (NMRI)	Altered spontaneous behavior and reduced habituation	320	3200	175 (7 x 2.5 x 10)	1.83
Xu et al., 2011	Oral to prepubertal offspring	Mouse (ICR)	Impaired passive avoidance memory	-	40	1750 (10 x 7 x 2.5 x 10)	0.023

- : not established

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Conclusion

The adverse effects on the mammary gland following developmental exposure have been assessed and considered to be taken into account in previous European reports. No individual study was however considered robust enough by EFSA or RAC to serve as a critical study for the identification of a starting point for a TDI or DNEL derivation. Nonetheless, several studies published after the ECHA and EFSA assessments suggest that BPA causes developmental effects at exposure levels far below the EFSA point of departure (POD). Some of these studies however have limitations in design and reporting and are not consistent with results obtained in other studies. It was decided to adopt the t-TDI value of 4 µg/kg bw/day (relating to a BMDL₁₀ of 8960 µg/kg bw/d for relative mean kidney weight increase observed in male F0 adult mice of the Tyl et al., 2008 study) for the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop}. However, as EFSA is currently re-assessing the hazards of BPA by reviewing the data published since December 2012 (the cut-off point of EFSA's latest assessment), the endpoint and POD selected to derive the TDI are likely to change in light of new available data. HBM-GVs are thereby subject to change accordingly.

4.2 For occupationally exposed workers

4.2.1 Existing OEL values for BPA

Table 8 summarises the existing OELs derived in Europe for BPA.

Table 8: Overview of existing OELs for BPA derived for the occupational field

Agency	Key study	Endpoint	POD	Assessment factors	OEL (8h-TWA)
SCOEL, 2014	Nitschke, 1988 (subchronic rat study, daily exposure to airborne BPA)	Respiratory tract irritation	NOAEC 10 mg/m ³	3 for interspecies extrapolation	2 mg/m³ (as inhalable dust)
The Netherlands Health Council, 2019	Nitschke, 1988 (subchronic rat study, daily exposure to airborne BPA)	Respiratory tract irritation	NOAEC 10 mg/m ³	3 for interspecies extrapolation	3.3 mg/m³ (inhalable fraction)
DFG, 1996 (updated 2011)	Nitschke, 1988 (subchronic rat study, daily exposure to airborne BPA)	Respiratory tract irritation	NOAEC 10 mg/m ³	2	5 mg/m³ (inhalable fraction)

4.2.1.1 SCOEL

The SCOEL considered the available data relating to inhalation exposure of BPA to derive an OEL. In the selected key study, rats were exposed daily to airborne BPA for 13 weeks (Nitschke et al., 1988). In this study, groups of 30 rats per sex were exposed via inhalation to 0, 10, 50 or 150 mg/m³ BPA for 6 hours/day, 5 days/week for 13 weeks. Animals were necropsied either on the day following the last exposure, or allowed to recover for 4 or 12 weeks. The following effects on organ weight were noted: decreased absolute liver weight in males at 10 or 150 mg/m³; decreased absolute liver and kidney weights in females exposed to 150 mg/m³; increased relative brain weights in females exposed to 50 or 150 mg/m³; and increased relative lung weights in females exposed to 150 mg/m³. These changes were not accompanied by microscopic changes. Enlarged ceca were found the day after exposure but were not apparent after 12 weeks recovery.

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Examination of the respiratory tract revealed very slight to slight epithelial hyperplasia and chronic inflammation of the submucosa in the nasal cavity of rats exposed to 50 or 150 mg/m³. These effects were fully reversible within 12 weeks after cessation of exposure. SCOEL identified a NOAEC of 10 mg/m³ for respiratory tract irritation and divided by an AF of 3 to cover the uncertainties related to the inter-species extrapolation in these local effects. The resulting OEL of 3 mg/m³ was further lowered to a recommended OEL of 2 mg/m³, by applying the so-called preferred value approach.

The SCOEL also noted that concern has been raised for systemic toxicity after long-term exposure. This was related to the effects on kidney weight and liver seen in rodents, for which a BMDL₁₀ of 3.5 mg/kg bw and a NOAEL of > 5 mg/kg bw was derived, respectively. According to the SCOEL, these doses are equivalent to an inhalation exposure level of 34 and 49 mg/m³, respectively. However, because the observed liver and kidney effects were very mild even at the highest dose levels, the recommended value was considered sufficiently conservative, covering also the extrapolation to long-term exposure, and possible remaining inter- and intra-species differences in toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics.

4.2.1.2 The Netherlands Health Council

In a draft report on Health-based recommendation on OELs, the Dutch Expert Committee on Occupational Safety performed a literature review of studies published after finalisation of EFSA's risk assessment on BPA in 2015. For data on adverse effects after inhalation exposure to BPA, only one recent animal study was identified (Chung et al., 2017), in which rats were exposed to 0, 10, 30, and 90 mg/m³ of BPA (particles ranging mostly from 2.10 to 7.0 µm) for 6 hr/day, 5 days/week for 8 weeks (equivalent to 1.4, 4.3 and 12.9 mg/kg bw). At the highest exposure concentration (90 mg/m³), slight but statistically significant decreases were observed for total serum cholesterol and adrenal gland weight. However, these effects were not considered adverse and there were no effects reported on the other endpoints studied (mortality, clinical signs, body weight, haematology, serum chemistry, oestrous cycle parameters, spatial learning and memory, organ weights, as well as gross and microscopic histopathological findings) in any of the male or female rats exposed to BPA. The Committee therefore uses the rat inhalation study by Nitschke et al. (1988), in which animals developed inflammation in the epithelium of the anterior portion of the nasal cavity. From this study, the Committee has derived a health-based advisory value of 3.3 mg/m³, which relates to the inhalable fraction (the fraction of the substance in air that can be inhaled through mouth and/or nose) and represents a mean concentration during an 8-h working day (Health Council of the Netherlands, 2019).

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4.2.2 Existing TRVs for BPA derived for workers

Table 9 summarises the existing TRVs derived in Europe for BPA.

Table 9: Overview of existing TRVs for BPA derived for the occupational field

Agency	Key study	Endpoint	POD	Assessment factors	TRV
ECHA, 2015	Tyl et al., 2008 (2-generation mouse toxicity study)	Increased relative mean kidney weight in F0 male adults	BMDL ₁₀ 8960 µg/kg bw/d (HED=609 with HEDF=0.068)	75 - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 5 for intraspecies differences - 6 for the uncertainty in the database	oral DNEL 8 µg/kg bw/d
			BMDL ₁₀ 8960 µg/kg bw/d (HED=6.64 or HED=6.24 with conversion factors 'oral mouse' to 'dermal human' either 1350.4 or 1436.9 depending upon PBPK model (Yang et al., 2013 or Mielke and Gundert-Remy, 2009))	75 - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 5 for intraspecies differences - 6 for the uncertainty in the database	DNEL for dermally absorbed total BPA dose 0.2 µg/kg bw/d (with biotransformation rate of 50%)

4.2.2.1 ECHA

The oral and dermal DNELs for workers proposed by ECHA are calculated as described in section 5.1.2 on the general population. However, as the default AF accounting for intraspecies differences is considering 5 for workers (instead of 10 for the general population), the DNEL values are two-fold the ones derived for the general population, i.e. 8 µg/kg bw/day for the oral DNEL for workers and 0.2 µg/kg bw/day for the dermal DNEL for workers.

Conclusion

Available OELs for BPA are based on respiratory tract irritation, thus not on systemic effects. It is consequently not relevant to determine the concentration of a biomarker of exposure consistent with any of these OELs.

The DNEL of 0.2 µg/kg bw/d for dermally absorbed BPA set by ECHA is of interest to determine the HBM-GV_{Worker}. It is based on the increased relative mean kidney weight observed in the male F0 adult mice of the Tyl et al., 2008 diet study, which was extrapolated through PBPK modelling to a human equivalent dermal dose considering the AUC of free BPA in serum as the relevant dose metric.

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5 HBM parameters

5.1 Choice of biomarkers

The concentration of free BPA in blood or plasma, which is available for interaction with the ER would be the dose metric most relevant to the mechanism of action, making the free form of BPA the toxicologically-relevant chemical form.

However, as BPA undergoes extensive first-pass hepatic metabolism via glucuronidation and sulphate formation (after oral exposure), blood and urine concentrations of free BPA following exposure to environmentally relevant doses of BPA are very low. Determination of these very low levels of free BPA in blood or plasma remains challenging due to analytical sensitivity issues (Dekant and Völkel, 2008), making its use as a biomarker at the present time difficult. The measurement of BPA as the end analyte can also lead to inaccurate estimates, from potential interferences from background sources and/or biological sample degradation (deconjugation of BPA) during handling in the field (Ye et al., 2013). Contamination by trace levels of BPA is so pervasive that even with extraordinary care, it is difficult to completely exclude the introduction of external BPA into biological samples (Buscher et al., 2015). Another concern of particular importance for the determination of free BPA levels, is the stability of BPA conjugates in biological samples during sample storage and processing (Dekant et al., 2008). It has been shown that BPA conjugates will spontaneously hydrolyse to form parent BPA in human urine (and likely serum) if stored at ambient temperatures for only short periods (Schöringhumer and Cichna-Markl, 2007; Ye et al., 2007).

BPA-G, as the major form of BPA present in blood (plasma) and in urine (Völkel et al., 2002, 2005) is a more specific biomarker as it requires *in vivo* metabolism to be produced and is not prone to external contamination. Therefore, it is considered a good candidate biomarker of exposure even though, from a mode of action perspective, this biomarker is expected to be much less informative than concentrations of free BPA in plasma or serum.

BPA-S is also a specific biomarker of exposure that can be measured in blood (plasma) and urine, but the frequency rate of detection is much lower than for BPA-G (Andra et al., 2016).

Both BPA-G and BPA-S however, are prone to inter-individual, inter-life stage and excretion compartment (e.g. breast milk versus urine) variability in BPA metabolism. Another limitation for their use is that conjugated forms could degrade within a day or two if the urine samples are stored at room temperature (Waechter et al., 2007; Ye et al., 2007; Hauck et al., 2016). This could lead to underestimation of BPA exposure if the conjugates alone are measured directly. Freezing the urinary samples prevents degradation, as indicated by the Hauck et al. (2016) study in which BPA-G was stable at -80 °C for 28 days and stable for at least 3 freeze and thaw cycles. However, even if stored correctly, exposure to ambient temperature for certain periods (sample collection, handling and shipping) is hardly avoidable (Andra et al., 2016).

Table 10: Potential biomarkers of exposure to BPA (Krisnan et al., 2010, adapted)

	Analyte	Molar mass	Biological matrix	Advantages	Disadvantages
Parent compound	Free BPA	228.3 g.mol ⁻¹	Blood	Would be expected to be highly relevant to potential adverse effects	Short half-life and low levels; invasive sampling required; possible background contamination of the samples
			Urine	Non-invasive	Little is excreted unchanged in urine; possible background contamination of the samples; not a good indicator of BPA in blood (poor correlation (r=0.51) between molar concentration of BPA in plasma and that in urine due to rapid metabolism (Ho et al., 2017))
Metabolite	BPA-G	BPA-MG: 404.4 g.mol ⁻¹ BPA-DG: 580.5 g.mol ⁻¹	Blood	-	Short half-life in humans; not directly relevant to mode of action; invasive sampling required.
			Urine	Major urinary metabolite for BPA; specific biomarker of exposure; non-invasive	Not directly relevant to mode of action
	BPA-S	BPA-MS 330.4 g.mol ⁻¹ BPA-DS 404.6 g.mol ⁻¹	Blood	-	Not detected in blood in human studies; not directly relevant to mode of action; invasive sampling required
			Urine	Specific biomarker of exposure; non-invasive	Less present than BPA-G; not directly relevant to mode of action

A good correlation ($r = 0.911$) between molar concentration of free BPA in the plasma and molar concentration of total BPA, i.e. the sum of free BPA and its main metabolites (BPA-G and BPA-S) was observed by Ho et al., 2017. Total BPA levels can be quantified by measuring free BPA in a sample that has been treated with appropriate enzymatic preparation, which cleaves the glucuronide and sulfate groups from the metabolites via hydrolysis.

Field blanks and procedural blanks are used as a quality control measure to assess and/or control background contamination of BPA when using total BPA as a biomarker, however no such measure is available to estimate the degradation of the urine sample between post-specimen collection and pre-analysis in the laboratory. Contamination with free BPA occurring during handling of the samples results in elevation of the aglycone BPA that subsequently contributes to inflated total BPA concentrations. Analytical methods to perform simultaneous determination of free BPA and its conjugates exist nowadays, which allow for summing the individually measured levels of aglycone and conjugated BPA forms to determine total BPA.

A good correlation was found between the total urinary content of BPA conjugates and the free BPA measured in plasma ($r = 0.896$) (Ho et al., 2017).

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Conclusion

Direct quantitation of specific BPA conjugates is currently only feasible thanks to the availability of analytical standards for these specific conjugates. However, not all the conjugated forms of BPA present in a sample can be quantified. Thus, it can be considered that a form of uncertainty in the estimation of the BPA present in a biological matrix is induced with this method.

The free form of BPA in plasma is the best biomarker to assess the link between BPA exposure and health effects, since it is the active form likely to induce adverse effects. Analytical methods to measure free BPA in plasma have recently become available and progress has been achieved regarding the QA/QC provisions to prevent external contamination with BPA. However, very few laboratories at this time have the capacity to perform this free BPA measurement, following the correct QA/QC criteria.

Therefore, the measurement of total BPA in urine (after a deconjugation step via an appropriate enzymatic preparation treatment of the sample), remains the best option to assess the exposure to BPA (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012). In 2018, the Inter-Laboratory Comparison Investigation (ICI) conducted for the analysis of BPA within the framework of the HBM4EU project was performed on total BPA in urine⁵.

5.2 Analytical methods

In numerous studies conducted to assess the BPA exposure levels in urine, the most common approach practiced is to measure the total BPA (free + conjugated forms) as well as the free form of BPA alone and then infer the conjugated levels (BPA-G and BPA-S) based on these measurements. This is in line with the recommendations of the German HBM Commission (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012). Analytical methods to determine the total concentration of BPA after enzymatic hydrolysis are performed, preferably at 37°C, for a few hours and in some cases overnight. In many studies, only the β -glucuronidase enzyme is used for the deconjugation step, because of the predominant presence of the glucuronide conjugate form of BPA. Few studies have additionally used sulfatase enzyme for the release of BPA from the sulfate conjugate that occurs as a minor fraction⁶ (Ye et al., 2005). Insufficient enzyme concentrations, inappropriate choice of enzymes, incomplete deconjugation, unfavorable hydrolysis conditions and overall suboptimal deconjugation protocol are some issues that may potentially lead to inaccurate measurement or underestimation of total BPA (Andra et al., 2016). However, this also applies to many other chemicals, and the introduction of adequate analytical QA/QC provisions allow adequate control of the efficiency of the deconjugation reaction. Finally, it is recommended that this issue should be better documented in published studies and better assessed in interlaboratory comparison and harmonisation assays, as it is foreseen within the HBM4EU initiative (WP9, Quality Assurance Unit and related dispositions).

Alternatively, recent advances in analytical methods and the commercial availability of analytical standards for BPA conjugates have now made the direct quantitation of specific BPA conjugates feasible. Methods to perform simultaneous analysis of BPA and its conjugates in urine or blood indeed started to being developed. The necessary analytical steps have been summarised and discussed by Andra et al. (2016). After sampling of urine, protein precipitation is performed as a pre-cleanup step using acetonitrile or methanol, which helps to minimise matrix effects and interference by both hydrophilic and hydrophobic molecules, even though analyte loss, induced by co-precipitation, is possible. Enzymatic deconjugation is not performed, so glucuronide and sulfate

⁵ ICI report on bisphenols available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/?mdocs-cat=mdocs-cat-27&mdocs-att=null>

⁶ In addition to the glucuronide form, sulfates are also deconjugated if the source of β -glucuronidase is from *Helix pomatia*-H1 compared to *Escherichia coli*-K12 (Ye et al., 2015)

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forms are recovered along with aglycone BPA from the sample. Some studies have also reported derivatisations with dansyl chloride, proposed to overcome the need for any further sample extraction steps and yet achieve desirable recoveries and detection limits for free and total BPA (Fox et al., 2011).

Further, isolation and pre-concentration of BPA and its conjugates in biological samples is achieved with either liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) or solid phase extraction (SPE) steps to not only enhance analyte recovery but also minimise matrix effects, prolong the life of the chromatography column and minimise the matrix residues deposit in the ionisation source and on the mass spectrometer detector.

Separation of the aglycone BPA and its conjugates has been performed using reversed-phase liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in a high majority of the available studies. For all studies without the derivatisation step, an electrospray ionisation mode was used. The presence of a phenolic hydroxyl functional group in aglycone BPA and its conjugates promotes efficient ionisation in the negative electrospray ionisation mode and was hence preferred in almost all studies, although the alternative GC-MS/MS approach can be also employed for free BPA with benefits in terms of sensitivity and lower backgrounds contamination issues (Deceuninck et al., 2014). Use of isotope-labeled internal standards in the very beginning of sample preparation ensures that matrix effects do not affect quantification significantly. Both deuterated and carbon isotope labeled BPA conjugate standards were used such as BPAG-d₁₆ (Völkel et al., 2005; Lacroix et al., 2011), BPAG-d₆ (Fox et al., 2011; Provencher et al., 2014), BPAG-¹³C₁₂ (Hauck et al., 2016; Vandenberg et al., 2014), and BPA-MS-d₆ and BPA-DS-d₆ (Provencher et al., 2014).

Reported lowest LOD values are 0.003 ng/mL for aglycone BPA in human urine (Liao and Kannan, 2012), 0.002 ng/mL for BPA-G in human serum (Vandenberg et al., 2014b) and 0.011 ng/mL for BPA-DS in human urine (Provencher et al., 2014; Andra et al., 2016).

Within the HBM4EU project, the published deliverable D9.2 “Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances” gives an insight into the analytical protocols and methods for HBM measurement of BPA in HBM4EU members’ states⁷. The techniques described are “LC-MS/MS preferably, GC-MS/MS as second relevant alternative, with different sample preparation and clean-up procedures (SPE, LLE, L-L, ultrasound, shaking, centrifugation, and derivatisation)”. LODs are usually between 0.003 and 0.15 ng/mL (except for a method using hair as a matrix (LOD = 1.8 ng/mL)). One study describes the use of a specific column “Glass AFFINIMIP® SPE Bisphenol A cartridge”, developed to selectively retain BPA, and the LOD (0.03 ng/mL) is comparable with the other methods. The amount of biological samples required by the different methods was 0.3-5 ml (urine), 0.3-2.5 mL (blood), 0.15-1.0 mL (hair), and 0.7 mL (saliva).

This deliverable also states that urine should be preferred as the matrix of choice for exposure assessment in the general population, while other matrices (e.g. serum or breast milk) are more of interest for gaining insights into mechanisms of toxicity. LOQ’s around 0.1 ng/mL (LOD’s around 0.03 ng/mL) are required for population-based studies. The risk of contamination of the samples during the sampling/preparation procedure should be monitored by field and laboratory blank controls.

⁷ Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>

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6 Derivation of HBM-GVs for BPA

6.1 Derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population

6.1.1 Derivation method

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} is derived by translating the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d from EFSA into the corresponding concentrations of the selected biomarker of exposure (i.e. total BPA in urine).

The modified PBPK model from Karrer et al. (2018) - described in the next section - was used to estimate the corresponding levels after two distinct scenarios of exposure (details in section 6.1.2):

- Scenario 1, assuming a constant and continuous exposure to the t-TDI of 4 µg BPA/kg bw/d, only via ingestion (100% oral exposure scenario);
- Scenario 2, assuming a constant and continuous exposure only via dermal absorption (100% cutaneous exposure scenario) leading to reach the plasmatic concentration of free BPA (as the known toxicologically active form) obtained from scenario 1.

As mentioned in section 2.5.1, the environmental exposure to BPA occurs by inhalation, oral and dermal routes. General population exposure estimates were calculated in various BPA risk assessments reports, as e.g. in the EFSA CEF Panel 2015 report. Average and high external exposure estimates to BPA from all sources in the general population indicated in this report are mentioned in Annex 3. Based on these estimates, the relative contributions of the ingestion, inhalation and dermal routes to the BPA total exposure can be calculated for different age- and gender- groups (Annex 3). According to these estimates, the inhalation route seems to contribute very little to the overall exposure to BPA (0.1% to 1.4% considering the average external exposure estimates). Thus, using the Karrer et al. PBPK model including both main routes of exposure (oral/dermal) to convert external exposure doses into internal concentrations of BPA would make possible to obtain estimates of the urinary total BPA concentration after mixed oral/dermal exposure scenarios (example described in Annex 3: the estimated concentration of total urinary BPA for an adult (18-45 years) after a constant exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw over a day resulting from a 70% oral and 30% dermal intake is 165 µg/L). However, considerable uncertainty is underlying the non-dietary sources exposure estimates (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). Therefore, it was decided not to suggest any HBM-GV_{GenPop} related to fixed percentages of the oral/dermal routes contributions to the total BPA exposure. Instead, boundary values of HBM-GV_{GenPop} for total BPA in urine corresponding to either 100% oral exposure (high boundary value) or 100% dermal exposure (low boundary value) are proposed.

Description of the PBPK model by Karrer et al. (2018)

Karrer et al. (2018) have modified the peroral adult PBPK model developed by Yang et al. (2015), that has been used by EFSA in 2015 for calculating the HEDF (ratio of AUC_{Animal}/AUC_{Human}) and further derive the t-TDI.

The modification consisted in recalibrating the model so that it corresponds well with a human kinetic data set (Thayer et al., 2015), incorporating an enterohepatic recirculation (EHR) pathway (conversion from unconjugated and glucuronidated substances, rate at 10%) and including the dermal route of exposure⁸. The schematic overview of the model is presented in Figure 2.

Based on the Karrer et al. (2018) model, a PBPK model for BPA and its metabolites (BPA-G and BPA-S) was implemented by Ineris within HBM4EU. The blood flow was replaced by a plasmatic

⁸ The authors also specify that while translating the language of the model, they identified a mistake in the published code of the PBPK model from Yang et al., 2015 (constant for the maximum velocity of glucuronidation in the gut not scaled up according to the bodyweight).

flow (BPA being mostly distributed in the plasma) and a value for the haematocrit of 0.45 was introduced. Outputs of excreted urinary BPA quantities were also replaced by urinary BPA concentrations, by adding an estimated value for the daily urinary excretion. A daily urinary excretion rate of 0.05L/h and 0.023 L/h were considered respectively for adults and children. After oral administration, an absorption fraction of 100% was considered. Regarding dermal uptake parameters, an absorption fraction of 60% and an absorption half-life of 0.167h were used (Biederman et al., 2010; Karrer et al., 2018).

Note: "Rich": richly perfused tissue; "slow": slowly perfused tissue
[perfusion higher/lower than 0:1 mL/min/g tissue, respectively]

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the PBPK model for BPA (also for BPS, BPF and BPAF) and their glucuronides and sulfates (PBPK-compartments in gray, single-compartment submodules with dotted lines) (Karrer et al., 2018)

Consideration of the type and time of HBM sampling is crucial, because the proposed HBM-GV_{GenPop} should allow for direct comparison with HBM urinary data on BPA collected in general population biomonitoring studies. Within HBM4EU, it is decided to derive a HBM-GV_{GenPop} for which interpretation of BPA exposure in a large population is possible provided spot-urine samples were collected at random times during the day, considering the arguments described below. It has to be noted though that high exposure is likely to be overestimated because spot urine sampling includes more sources of variability (e.g. within-person, within-day variability) than 24-hour urine sampling and that generic values in that case are generally used for the urinary output rate and bodyweight.

24-hour urine collections would be preferable, as both the urinary concentration of total BPA and the urinary output rate (mL/day) are measured in 24-hour urine samples (in addition to the individual's body weight), allowing the calculation of 24-hour BPA excretion for each individual. The GM (or median) can directly be used as an estimate for the average exposure of the population, whereas the 95th percentile might tend to overestimate the high exposure, as it includes not only

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the between-person variability but also the within-person between-day variation (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). However, collecting 24-h urine voids in large biomonitoring studies is rarely feasible, mainly for reasons of cost and logistics.

The collection of first morning urine is a non-random, single-sample sampling that is not representative of the daily variability. It bears the potential of introducing a bias and may result in an over- or underestimation of average exposure, although the sparse evidence available from the literature indicates comparability of the central tendency between first morning voids, spot urine samples and 24-hour urine samples (Christensen et al., 2012; EFSA CEF Panel, 2015, Vernet et al., 2018).

The urinary concentration of total BPA of an individual spot urine sample cannot be used to arrive at a realistic estimate of daily BPA exposure, because of the non-persistent nature and short elimination half-life of BPA (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). However, a set of spot urine samples can be used to obtain a reliable estimate of the average BPA exposure of a sufficiently large investigated population, provided that the sampling is at random in relation to meal ingestion and bladder-emptying times (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). Vernet et al., 2018, who characterised the within-day, between-day and between-week variability of phenol urinary biomarker concentrations (e.g. BPA) during pregnancy, came to the same conclusion that for biomonitoring purposes (and not etiological studies), collecting spot biospecimens was a good option if the population was large enough.

6.1.2 Prediction of the total BPA urinary concentration consistent with the t-TDI of EFSA

6.1.2.1 Scenario 1 - 100% oral exposure

For a male adult of 70 kg

The concentration of free BPA in plasma estimated under scenario 1 (assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPA to 4 µg/kg bw) for a male adult of 70 kg is illustrated in Figure 3. **The maximum concentration of free plasmatic BPA estimated is 0.03 nmol/L (6.8 ng/L).**

Figure 3: Estimated free BPA (and total BPA) plasmatic concentrations (nmol/L) for a 70 kg adult after constant and continuous oral exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over 24h

The concentrations of total and free BPA in urine predicted under scenario 1 for a male adult of 70 kg after constant and continuous oral exposure is illustrated in Figure 4. The **estimated concentration of total BPA in urine is 1022 nmol/L (233 µg/L)**; whereas the estimated concentration of free BPA in urine is 0.9 nmol/L (0.2 µg/L).

Figure 4: Estimated urinary total BPA (and free BPA) concentrations (nmol/L) for a 70 kg adult after constant and continuous oral exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over 24h

For a 5 year-old child of 19 kg

The concentration of free BPA in plasma predicted under scenario 1 (assuming a constant and continuous oral exposure throughout the day of BPA to 4 µg/kg bw) for a 5 year-old child of 19 kg is illustrated in Figure 5. **The concentration of free plasmatic BPA estimated is 0.06 nmol/L (13.7 ng/L).**

Figure 5: Estimated free BPA (and total BPA) plasmatic concentrations (nmol/L) for a 19 kg child (5 years of age) after constant and continuous oral exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over 24h

The concentrations of total and free BPA in urine predicted under scenario 1 for a 5 years-old child of 19 kg is illustrated in Figure 6. The **estimated concentration of total BPA in urine is 603 nmol/L (137 µg/L)**; whereas the maximum concentration of free BPA estimated in urine is 1.5 nmol/L (0.3 µg/L).

Figure 6: Estimated urinary total BPA (and free BPA) concentrations (nmol/L) for a 19 kg child (5 years of age) after constant and continuous oral exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over 24h

6.1.2.2 Scenario 2 - 100% dermal exposure

For a male adult of 70 kg

The chemical form exerting the toxicity of BPA is likely to be the free BPA in plasma. Therefore, the concentration of free plasmatic BPA estimated through Scenario 1, i.e. 0.03 nmol/L (6.8 ng/L), is considered as a threshold level above which adverse effects due to BPA could occur. The dermal dose of exposure necessary to generate this same free BPA plasmatic concentration was determined (0.175 µg/bw/kg) and applied in the PBPK model⁹. **The resulting estimated concentration of total BPA in urine is 27 nmol/L (6.2 µg/L)** (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Estimated urinary total BPA (and free BPA) concentrations (nmol/L) for a 70 kg adult after constant and continuous dermal exposure generating the same concentration of free BPA in plasma than after a 100% oral intake of 4 µg/kg bw averaged over 24h (Scenario 1)

⁹ The BPA dermal absorption fraction (%) considered for the simulations is 60%, as estimated by Biedermann et al. 2010 for exposure to BPA via personal care products (see Table 4).

For a 5 year-old child of 19 kg

The concentration of free plasmatic BPA estimated through Scenario 1, which is considered as a threshold level above which adverse effects due to BPA could occur, is 0.06 nmol/L ($13.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ µg/L). The dermal dose of exposure necessary to generate this same free BPA plasmatic concentration was applied in the PBPK model. **The concentration of total BPA in urine estimated is 56 nmol/L (12.8 µg/L)** (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Estimated urinary total BPA (and free BPA) concentrations (nmol/L) for a 19 kg child after constant and continuous dermal exposure generating the same concentration of free BPA in plasma than after a 100% oral intake of 4 µg/kg bw averaged over 24h (Scenario 1)

6.1.3 Conclusion on the HBM-GV_{GenPop} proposal

Table 11 summarises the boundary values for the concentration of total BPA in urine consistent with the concentration of free BPA in plasma after exposure to the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d, either after 100% oral (high boundary value) or 100% dermal exposure (low boundary value). The high boundary value is retained as the maximum limit value (HBM-GV_{GenPop}). It has to be acknowledge however, that it is not particularly conservative, only considering oral exposure. Environmental exposure of the general population is likely to occur by inhalation, dermal and oral routes, which would generate a lower limit value for total BPA in urine than after oral exposure only, even when considering the same external health-based tolerable daily dose.

Table 11: Boundary values for total BPA in urine consistent with the concentration of free BPA in plasma after either 100% oral or 100% dermal exposure to the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d

Population group	High boundary value for total BPA in urine (assuming 100% oral exposure to BPA) → HBM-GV _{GenPop}	Low boundary value for total BPA in urine (assuming 100% dermal exposure to BPA)	Corresponding concentration of free BPA in plasma
Adult (45 years, 70 kg)	233 µg/L	6.2 µg/L	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ µg/L
Child (5 years, 19 kg)	137 µg/L	12.8 µg/L	$13.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ µg/L

The calculated HBM-GVs (high boundary values) are in the same range as the German HBM-I values for total urinary BPA from 2015 (adults: 0.2 mg BPA /L urine, children: 0.1 mg BPA /L urine), which are also based on the EFSA TDI value released in 2015. It was assumed that the oral BPA intake corresponds to an almost total renal elimination and that the range of variation is

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sufficiently covered by the assumptions on the mean age-specific urine excretion amounts (with default values set for the urine volumes of 0.02 L/kg bw for adults and 0.03 L/kg bw for children) (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2012 and 2015; Apel et al., 2016).

Calculations of urinary total BPA limit values were also performed by the biomonitoring equivalent approach (obtaining the selected biomarker concentration consistent with the t-TDI from EFSA 2015), but using a simple urinary mass balance equation. Results are indicated in Annex 4. The concentration of total BPA in urine for a male adult which is obtained by this approach is 168 µg/L, i.e. slightly less than the value of 233 µg/L obtained with the use of the modified Karrer et al. PBPK model after 100% oral exposure (same order of magnitude nevertheless).

6.2 Derivation of HBM-GVs for workers

6.2.1 Derivation method

Human data do not allow for consistently identifying a relationship between kidney effects (critical effect supporting the t-TDI value from EFSA) and HBM measurements of BPA either in urine or in plasma. The second option to derive a HBM-GV_{worker} value (HBM4EU concept document, publication in preparation) is to assess whether a relevant OEL or TRV can be translated into (a) corresponding concentration(s) of the selected biomarker(s), provided there is a statistically significant correlation between atmospheric (or dermal) levels of the parent compound and its biomarker(s) of exposure concentrations demonstrated at the workplace..

Correlation studies between air, urine and hand measures of BPA in the occupational field

He et al. (2009) examined the correlation between BPA concentrations in personal air samples and in pre- and post-shift urine samples from 131 epoxy resin- and BPA-manufacturing workers in China. They found Spearman coefficients of 0.525 (air with pre-shift urine) and 0.726 (air with post-shift urine) although air and urine samples were not always collected on the same day.

Ndaw et al. (2016) evaluated the exposure to BPA in 90 cashiers and in 44 non-occupationally exposed workers from several places. Urinary BPA was quantified as free and total forms in 24-h and spot urine samples using LC-MS/MS. Cashiers had a median urinary total BPA concentration of 8.92 µg/L (6.76 µg/g creatinine) (versus controls: 3.54 µg/L (2.89 µg/g creatinine)) and a median urinary free BPA concentration (analysed directly) of 0.28 µg/L (0.22 µg/g creatinine) (versus controls 0.20 µg/L (0.21 µg/g creatinine)). No correlation was found between the urinary concentration levels and the number of BPA-containing thermal receipts handled (highly variable among cashiers and depending on the workplace).

Kouidhi et al. (2017) recently observed that urinary concentrations of total BPA obtained from 70 workers of a plastic molding factory in Malaysia were significantly correlated with airborne BPA levels ($p=0.55$, $p<0.01$). The correlation test considered the airborne BPA concentrations at the staying position of the workers operating the machine as the individual exposure level (mean BPA concentration of 16.40 ± 5.95 ng/m³). The mean urinary concentration of total BPA sampled at the end of the workers shift was $3.88 (\pm 2.65)$ ng/ml.

Hines et al. (2018) assessed the relationship among urine, air and hand measures of exposure to BPA in 78 US manufacturing workers. Urine samples were taken from participants over 2 consecutive days, with following time points: pre-shift (where possible after the participant had been off work for at least 24 h, for having the baseline value), mid-shift, end-shift and post-shift (4–6 h after leaving work) on Day 1 and pre-shift, mid-shift and end-shift on Day 2. Urinary concentrations of total BPA were obtained by online SPE-HPLC-isotope dilution tandem mass spectrometry (LOD = 0.1 µg/L) and adjusted to measured urinary creatinine. The GM of the total BPA was 88.0 µg/g creatinine and ranged between 0.78 and 18 900 µg/g¹ creatinine (Hines et al., 2017a). For each participant, full-shift breathing zone air samples (inhalable aerosol fraction) were

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collected on each of the 2 days and a pre-shift and end-shift hand-wipe samples were collected on Day 2 (except for one worker on Day 1). Air and wipe samples were extracted with acetonitrile and analysed for BPA by HPLC with ultraviolet detection ($LOD_{air} = 0.03$ to $0.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$; $LOD_{hand\ wipe} = 0.05$ to $0.3 \mu\text{g}$ per sample). End-shift total creatinine-corrected BPA strongly correlated with BPA in air ($r_p = 0.79$, $P < 0.0001$) and nearly as strongly with BPA in end-shift hand wipes ($r_p = 0.75$, $P < 0.0001$). In mixed-effect models, air concentration of BPA and end-shift hand-wipe BPA level were significantly and positively associated with end-shift total creatinine-corrected BPA ($p < 0.0001$ each). Mixed-effects regression modeling indicated that the model fit improved when the model included only the BPA air concentration compared with when the model had only the BPA hand-wipe level (holding all other terms constant). This could suggest that inhalation was a more important exposure route, on average, than dermal contact for this group of workers (although both measures were statistically significant in all models), which was consistent with higher BPA intake estimates based on inhalation than on dermal exposure in these workers (Hines et al., 2017b).

6.2.2 HBM-GVs for occupationally exposed adults

Despite the fact that inhalation seems to be the most important route of BPA exposure for workers, data characterising the toxicokinetic of BPA after inhalation in humans is lacking. It is presumed that a fraction of inhaled BPA is actually absorbed by the oral route and is thus subject to first-pass hepatic metabolism. However, due to the paucity of kinetic data regarding the inhalation route and the fact that all existing OELs are based on non-systemic respiratory effects, it is not possible to derive a $HBM-GV_{worker}$ based on atmospheric levels to BPA likely to induce toxic effects at the workplace.

The DNEL for dermally absorbed BPA dose for workers set by ECHA (2015) could have been considered as starting point for the $HBM-GV_{worker}$ derivation. However, this value was set after route-to-route extrapolation¹⁰ of the $BMDL_{10}$ of $8960 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ for increased relative mean kidney weight in mice exposed by gavage and further assuming a skin biotransformation rate for BPA of 50%. Taking advantage of the modified PBPK model from Karrer et al., which includes the oral and dermal route of exposure, the concentration of total BPA in urine after dermal exposure to BPA was rather estimated based on the plasmatic concentration of free BPA (e.g. the toxicologically-relevant chemical form) generated after oral exposure to the t-TDI of $4 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$.

Considering the simulation performed for an adult from the general population (men 45 years, 70 kg), a constant 24h-averaged exposure to $4 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ of BPA by oral intake is leading to **a free BPA plasmatic concentration of 6.8 ng/L**. The external dose via dermal exposure leading to this concentration is $0.175 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$ according to the modified Karrer et al. model, i.e. very close to the $DNEL_{worker}$ of $0.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$ set by ECHA for a dermally absorbed BPA dose (ECHA, 2015). The resulting concentration of total BPA in urine after **a constant and continuous 100% dermal intake scenario is 6.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$** .

Simulation of a constant dermal exposure to BPA, but this time corresponding to an occupational exposure scenario (i.e. 8 working hours/day over a working week i.e. 5 consecutive working days/week), was also performed (see Annex 5). By setting the concentration of **free BPA in plasma at 6.8 ng/L at the end of the shift and working week**, as limit value not to be exceeded, the corresponding **urinary concentration of total BPA** obtained is **5.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$** (25 nmol/L).

This limit value of $5.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ total BPA in urine is lower than most of the P95 of the urinary total BPA levels distribution measured in adults from the EU general population, which is ranging from 5 to $14 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ (Annex 1). Thus, biomonitoring using total BPA in urine as biomarker of dermal exposure

¹⁰ with calculation of a conversion factor from oral mouse doses to dermal human doses, obtained by PBPK model-based predictions of the AUC for unconjugated BPA in serum in adults for an oral dose of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ and for a dermally absorbed dose of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$

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cannot be used to identify occupational exposure at risk, considering the high background levels of individuals originating mostly from their non-occupational oral intake.

The value of 6.8 ng/L free BPA in plasma at the end of shift and working week could be considered as HBM-GV_{worker}, however even if considering that progress has been achieved regarding the analytical capacities to measure free BPA in plasma complying with QA/QC requirements, very few laboratories at this time have the capacity to perform quantification of low-levels of free BPA levels in plasma with confidence.

Therefore, no HBM-GV_{worker} is recommended for the effective control of the health risks related to BPA in the practice of occupational health. The EU reference value for workers that will be established for BPA under T10.4 of HBM4EU should be rather used to assess whether the exposure at the workplace is adequately controlled or not¹¹. Sampling of total BPA in urine at the beginning of the working shift and week compared to sampling at the end of the working shift can be useful to recognise what the workplace exposure adds to the exposure occurring by food intake.

¹¹ If a biomonitoring result is greater than an EU reference value for workers, it does not necessarily mean that ill health will occur, but it does indicate that control of exposure may not be adequate. Under these circumstances, employers will need to look at current work practices to see how they can be improved to reduce exposure.

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7 Level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept paper to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the derivation of the value and could constitute a good incentive to later revise values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} are set to '**medium**'. Please refer to note n°2 of the factsheet presented in section 8 for explanation on this level of confidence.

An HBM-GV_{Worker} is not derived. When considering only dermal exposure at the workplace, the limit value for total BPA in urine is below or at the level of the P95 concentrations of total urinary BPA for adults from the general population. A limit value based on realistic estimates of relative contributions of exposure pathways at the workplace (occurring through dermal intake, inhalation and through hands-to-mouth behavior) might be derived, provided such estimates are made available.

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8 Factsheet

Factsheet reporting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation

Bisphenol A (BPA)		Target population General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	HBM-GV Adults, for total BPA in urine: 233 µg/L HBM-GV Children, for total BPA in urine: 137 µg/L	
Level of confidence	2	Medium	
HBM-GV status	3	Provisional	
HBM-GV year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	604-030-00-0	
EC-Nr.	6	201-245-8	
CAS-Nr.	7	80-05-7	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	- Repr. 1B - H360F - STOT SE 3 - H335 - Skin Sens. 1 - H317 - Eye Dam 1 - H318	- may damage fertility - may cause respiratory irritation - may cause an allergic skin reaction - causes serious eye damage
Molar mass	9	228.29 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Total BPA in urine	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	228.29 g/mol	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	12	Approximately 6 hours	Völkel et al. 2002, 2005
Derivation method, starting point and assessment factors			
Type of derivation method selected	13	Translation of t-TDI value of 4 µg/kg bw/d into urinary total BPA concentration	Use of the modified PBPK model of Karrer et al. 2018
Key study	14	Tyl et al. 2008 Two-generation reproductive toxicity study of dietary bisphenol a in CD-1 (Swiss) mice	
Exposure route of study	15	Oral (in feed)	0, 0.003, 0.03, 0.3, 5, 50, or 600 mg BPA/kg bw/day in feed
Critical endpoint and POD	16	Increased relative mean kidney weight in F0 male adults BMDL ₁₀ : 8960 µg/kg bw/d	
Extrapolations and AFs	17	HED = 609 µg BPA/kg bw/d with HEDF = 0.068 Global AF of 150 (2.5 for interspecies differences; 10 for intraspecies	Comparison of AUC with PBPK model from Yang et al., 2013

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Bisphenol A (BPA)		Target population General population	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
		differences; 6 for the uncertainty in the database)	
Calculation of HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
PBPK model for translating the selected exposure guidance value to an internal guidance value	18	Modified model from Karrer et al., 2018 PBPK Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with its Substitutes	Constant exposure to 24h-averaged t-TDI of 4 µg BPA/kg bw
Rounded value of HBM-GV_{Genpop}		HBM-GV_{GenPop, Adults} for total BPA in urine: 233 µg/L HBM-GV_{Genpop, Children} for total BPA in urine: 137 µg/L	
Additional Comments			

Explanation of notes

- 1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: rounded numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in µg/L
- 2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derivate the toxicity reference value (TRV), uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed BPA HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the BPA epidemiological and/or toxicological data: BPA is a well-known toxicant for male reproductive physiology in animal models, but data in humans are quite controversial (exposure doses, duration and routes, as well as life stage affecting its effects on reproductive health). The BPA toxicological database is extended, however, discrepancies in outcomes among and between studies with BPA, in particular between standard guideline studies on one side and a large number of small scale *in vitro* and *in vivo* research or experimental studies addressing novel endpoints on the other side, has often led to controversy → **low confidence**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: using a WoE approach, the critical endpoint retained by EFSA to derive the t-TDI is the kidney effect in adult mice (EFSA, 2015). Regarding the mode of action, EFSA recommended that mechanistic studies in the kidney should be performed, to determine the mode of action of BPA in this organ. However, since then, recent scientific literature has provided additional indications of reproductive and developmental effects at doses of BPA below the NOAEL for general toxicity, but also neurological/ neurodevelopmental/ neuroendocrine, immune-modulatory and metabolic effects, and EFSA committed to reevaluate accordingly its t-TDI. The CEF Panel considered the effects on the developing mammary gland as 'likely' and TRVs based on this endpoint that were derived by e.g. ANSES or KEMI are lower than the current t-TDI → **low confidence**
 - the selected key study and POD: because analysis of the mammary gland data revealed large differences in the BMD estimates and wide BMD confidence intervals obtained with some of the

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models, these estimates could not be used for the derivation of the t-TDI. The CEF Panel therefore used the endpoint “general toxicity” for risk characterisation, specifically the mean relative kidney weight in a two-generation study in mice (Tyl et al. 2008), and calculated a BMDL₁₀ of 8960 µg/kg bw per day. The Tyl et al. 2008 study follows OECD guidelines undertaken in accordance with good laboratory practice. According to EFSA recommendations¹² however, a default 5% BMR is recommended for continuous data. Setting the BMR at 5% would have decreased the t-TDI value → **medium confidence**

- the route-to-route, inter- and intra-species extrapolations: The t-TDI from EFSA already includes AFs accounting for intra- and interspecies differences (respectively 10 and 2.5). The modified human PBPK model from Karrer et al. 2018 was used to determine the total BPA in urine consistent with this t-TDI. Making profit of the PBPK model that includes the oral and dermal routes of exposure, urinary total BPA values can be set according to estimated relative contributions of both routes of exposure → **medium confidence**
- the calculation of the HBM-GVs: the determination of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} is based on a continuous exposure to the 24h-averaged t-TDI, not reflecting the likely environmental exposure to BPA that is rather occurring by peaks of exposure. A high boundary value for total BPA in urine is proposed (consistent with a 100% oral intake scenario), which does not completely reflect the most likely environmental exposure occurring mainly by oral, but also by inhalation and dermal absorption → **medium confidence**

Altogether, the global level of confidence for the BPA HBM-GVs in the general population is set to ‘**medium**’.

- 3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is fixed to ‘provisional’, thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data are reduced.
- 4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the frame of HBM4EU.
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduitory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System: <https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>
- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of BPA per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as relevant for interpreting exposures to BPA from population- or cohort-based biomonitoring studies is total BPA in urine.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker: mass of the selected biomarker (expressed in g/mol)

¹² <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2009.1150>

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- 12) Excretion half-life of selected biomarker: around 6h, according to volunteer-based studies from Völkel et al. 2002 and 2005.
- 13) Type of derivation method selected: human-based data on BPA are controversial; therefore, a review of existing TRV was performed, in order to derive an HBM-GV consistent with one of these values. The t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d from EFSA (2015) was selected and set as input parameter as 24-h averaged exposure dose in a BPA human PBPK model, to obtain the corresponding urinary total BPA concentration.
- 14) Key study: the key study underlying the selected t-TDI is the two-generation reproductive toxicity study of dietary BPA in CD-1 (Swiss) mice from Tyl et al. 2008.
- 15) Exposure route: Tyl et al. 2008 examined dietary BPA in a CD-1 mice (n=28 per group) at 0, 0.003, 0.03, 0.3, 5, 50, or 600 mg BPA/kg bw/d in feed.
- 16) Critical effect and POD: the selected critical endpoint concerns the relative mean kidney weight in the mouse, for which a BMDL₁₀ of 8960 µg/kg bw/d was derived. Kidney weights have been evaluated as mean kidney weight per animal (i.e. left + right kidney weight divided by 2). Relative kidney weights are the mean kidney weights divided by the body weight.
- 17) Extrapolations and AFs: a human equivalent dose factor (HEDF) of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice was applied to the BMDL₁₀ of 8960 µg/kg b/d, which results in a HED of 609 µg/kg bw. An AF of 2.5 for interspecies differences (1 for toxicokinetics and 2.5 for toxicodynamics, reflecting the fact that toxicokinetic differences have been addressed by use of the HED approach), an AF of 10 for intraspecies differences and an extra AF of 6 to account for the uncertainty in the database (i.e. mammary gland and reproductive, neurobehavioural, immune and metabolic systems) were applied.
- 18) According to the modified Karrer et al. 2018 PBPK model, the concentrations of total BPA in urine corresponding to a 24h-averaged t-TDI exposure through a 100% oral intake are:

HBM-GV_{GenPop} for adults = 233 µg/L

HBM-GV_{GenPop} for children = 137 µg/L

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9 Discussion

The extensive database on BPA provides convincing evidence of adverse effects on reproductive, neurobehavioural, metabolic functions and mammary gland. Disruption of estrogenic signalling is central in the mediation of these effects although other modes of action may be involved (Almeida et al., 2018, Le Magueresse-Battistoni et al. 2018, Mhaouty-Kodja et al. 2018)

However, despite the extensive database on BPA, uncertainties remain considering dose-response. The sensitivity to BPA is clearly dependent on the timing of exposure, with specific periods of development being critical and it is not excluded that non-monotonic dose-responses may exist. Understanding all the parameters that influence the dose-response to BPA in any case represents a challenge for its risk assessment (Pouzaud et al., 2018).

BPA deleterious effects should be better defined in vulnerable populations, such as foetuses, infants and young children, where also a mixture of different environmental chemical pollutants may affect the correct tissue development and organogenesis. The embryonic critical window of exposure can involve systemic metabolic homeostasis and adulthood health programming, in agreement with the new concept of “developmental origins of health and disease”, which underlies foetal basis for adult diseases (Alonso-Magdalena et al., 2015; Valentino et al., 2016).

The EFSA CEF Panel designated its t-TDI set in 2015 as temporary, pending the outcome of the long-term study in rats involving prenatal as well as postnatal exposure to BPA being undertaken by NTP/FDA. As this temporary value underlies the HBM-GVs derivation proposed in this document, proposed HBM-GVs should also be regarded as interim screening values that would have to be modified according to the possible update of the existing TRVs set by the scientific and regulatory community.

Because of BPA's short elimination half-life, strategies to address the large variability in BPA concentrations of spot urine samples need to be developed to adequately categorise exposure as appropriate to the end-point of interest. When the population investigated is sufficiently large (e.g. nationally representative population-based surveys), the spot sampling approach may provide enough statistical power to categorise the average population exposure to BPA. For purposes other than population-based surveys, biomonitoring data would be strengthened by the collection of multiple (rather than single) spot urine samples, particularly in studies aimed at evaluating the potential impact of exposure to BPA on human health. Furthermore, the study design should consider the impact of time of day of sampling (e.g. in relation to consumption of food) and time of last urination as important exposure contributors to provide the best approach for BPA exposure assessment (WHO, 2011).

The currently scarce available kinetic data of BPA internal exposure via dermal or inhalation contact make the derivation of an HBM-GV for workers very challenging. Effective control of the health risks related to BPA in the practice of occupational health should rather be performed at present by referring to the EU reference value for workers that will be set within HBM4EU project. Derivation of an HBM-GV_{worker} using total urinary BPA as biomarker of exposure is conditioned by a better understanding of the exposure pathways occurring at the workplace. The alternative option would be to set an HBM-GV_{worker} for free BPA in plasma, at the time analytical capacities will allow for high-level confidence measurements complying with QA/QC requirements. Verification of the predictive ability of available PBPK models on BPA would also benefit from high-confidence datasets on free BPA low-levels in plasma.

Therefore, the development of analytical methods that would better document the BPA plasma free fraction, based on technological advances and necessary investment in this aspect of exposure characterisation, is strongly encouraged.

10 Annexes

10.1 Annex 1 - Overview of BPA levels in urine and serum retrieved in individuals from the general population in HBM4EU participating countries

Total urinary BPA						
Cohort	Country	Survey date	Number of individuals	P95 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Comments	Reference
Esteban	France	2014-2016	231 children (6-10y)	7.33	First morning urine sample	SPF, 2019
			175 adolescents (11-14y)	13.71		
			94 adolescents (15-17y)	6.00		
			55 Adults (18-29y)	8.23		
			224 adults (30-44y)	10.97		
			345 adults (45-59y)	7.61		
			276 adults (60-74y)	5.34		
Democophes	Belgium	2011-2012	125 mothers (\leq 45y)	11.63	First-morning urine samples	Covaci et al., 2015
			125 children (5-12y)	13.44		
	Denmark		143 mothers (\leq 45y)	11.45		
			142 children (5-12y)	7.90		
	Luxembourg		56 mothers (\leq 45y)	7.44		
			59 children (5-12y)	8.28		
	Slovenia		106 mothers (\leq 45y)	13.35		
			112 children (5-12y)	18.90		

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Total urinary BPA						
Cohort	Country	Survey date	Number of individuals	P95 (µg/L)	Comments	Reference
	Spain		113 mothers (≤ 45y)	12.20		
			118 children (5-12y)	9.80		
	Sweden		96 mothers (≤ 45y)	5.02		
			97 children (5-12y)	6.24		
PBAT	Austria	2010-2012	594 participants (6-79y)	3.70	Urine samples collected before midday	Hartmann et al., 2016
Odense Child Cohort	Denmark	2006-2012	565 pregnant women (18-42y)	7.52	Spot urine sample	Frederiksen et al., 2014
ELFE	France	2011	1764 pregnant women (> 18y)	5.28	Spot urine samples (at arrival at the maternity)	Dereumeaux et al., 2016
EDEN		2003-2006	520 pregnant women	11.0	First morning urine (or if forgotten, spot urine samples) 4	Philippat et al., 2014
RefLim2011	Finland	2011	121 adults (22-67y)	7.90	Spot urine samples	Porras, et al. 2014
GerES IV	Germany	2003-2006	599 children (3-14y)	14.0	Morning urine samples	Becker et al., 2009
ESB		2009	60 students (20-29y)	7.07	24h urine samples	Koch et al., 2012
Duisburg birth cohort study		2007-2009	104 mothers	8.40	First morning urine sample	Kasper-Sonnenberg et al., 2012
	104 children		9.70			
RHEA	Greece	2009-2011	103 pregnant women (>16y)	4.70	Spot urine samples	Myridakis et al., 2015
			136 children (4y)	16.60		
IBMS	Israel	2011	246 adults (20-75y)	18.78	Spot urine samples	Berman et al., 2014
InCHIANTI	Italy	1998-2000	720 adults (20-74y)	11.50	24h urine samples	Galloway et al., 2010

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Total urinary BPA						
Cohort	Country	Survey date	Number of individuals	P95 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Comments	Reference
Generation R	The Netherlands	2004-2006	100 pregnant women (18-41y)	8.60	Spot urine sample	Ye et al. 2008
INMA	Spain	2004-2006	479 pregnant women (1st and 3rd trimester, ≥ 16 y)	11.90	Maternal spot urine samples	Casas et al., 2013

Free urinary BPA						
Cohort	Country	Survey date	Number of individuals	P95 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Comments	Reference
Esteban	France	2014-2016	231 children (6-10y)	0.266	First morning urine sample	SPF, 2019
			175 adolescents (11-14y)	0.220		
			94 adolescents (15-17y)	0.125		
			55 Adults (18-29y)	0.312		
			224 adults (30-44y)	0.246		
			345 adults (45-59y)	0.232		
			276 adults (60-74y)	0.241		

Serum BPA						
Cohort	Country	Survey date	Number of individuals	Mean \pm SD ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Comments	Reference
PIVUS	Sweden	<i>Not specified</i>	1003 adults aged 70y	4.94 \pm 4.31	P95 not indicated	Olsén et al., 2012

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10.2 Annex 2 - Description of the Tyl et al. 2002 and 2008 studies (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)

Tyl et al. (2002) exposed **CD Sprague-Dawley rats** (n = 20 females per group) to dietary BPA in a 3-generation study at 0, 0.015, 0.3, 4.5, 75, 750, 7 500 ppm (giving doses of approximately 0, 0.02, 0.3, 5, 50 and 500 mg/kg bw per day). The exposure started 10 weeks before mating and continued during mating, gestation and lactation until weaning. At weaning (PND21), 30 animals/sex/dose were randomly selected as F1 parents, and exposed to BPA as described for the F0 generation. The selection, number and treatment of the F2 parents were performed as described for the F1 parents. Adult systemic toxicity at 750 and 7 500 ppm in all generations included: reduced body weights and body weight gains, reduced absolute and increased relative weanling and adult organ weight (liver, kidney, adrenals, spleen, pituitary and brain), and mild renal (tubular degeneration) and hepatic pathology (in females only). Reproductive organ histology and function were unaffected, except for reduced ovarian weights, a significantly reduced number of implantation sites and decreased number of pups/litter on PND 0 at 7500 ppm. In the F1, F2 and F3 offspring vaginal patency and preputial separation were delayed, associated with reduced body weight. Adult systemic NOAEL was 5 mg/kg bw per day and reproductive and postnatal NOAELs were 50 mg/kg bw per day.

Tyl et al. (2008) examined dietary BPA in a **CD-1 mice** (n=28 per group) 2-generation study at 0, 0.018, 0.18, 1.8, 30, 300, or 3 500 ppm in feed (giving 0, 0.003, 0.03, 0.3, 5, 50, or 600 mg BPA/kg bw per day). 17 β -oestradiol (0.5 ppm) was used as positive control. There were no BPA related effects on adult mating, fertility or gestational indices, ovarian primordial follicle counts, oestrous cyclicity, precoital interval, offspring sex ratios or postnatal survival, sperm parameters or reproductive organ weights or histology. Systemic effects in adults were increased kidney and liver weight, centrilobular hepatocyte hypertrophy, and nephropathy and statistically significant reduction in epididymal sperm concentration (15% reduction) in both F0 and F1 males at 3500 ppm (600 mg/kg bw per day). Centrilobular hepatocyte hypertrophy was also apparent in F0 males at 50 mg BPA/kg bw per day), and kidney weight was statistically significantly increased at this dose level in both F0 and F1 males, while in F1 males there was also a statistically significant increase in kidney weight in animals receiving 0.3 or 5 mg/kg bw per day. Female mice were less sensitive to these effects. Increased kidney and liver weight and centrilobular hepatocyte hypertrophy were observed in F0 females at 3 500 ppm (600 mg/kg bw per day), but nephropathy was not evident on histopathological examination, and centrilobular hypertrophy was the only treatment related change reported in the F1 females. At 3 500 ppm (600 mg/kg bw per day) BPA also reduced F1/F2 weanling body weight, reduced weanling spleen and testes weight (with seminiferous tubule hypoplasia). At lower doses (0.018 to 30 ppm) there were no treatment related effects in adults or F1/F2 offspring. There are no obvious weaknesses in this study.

10.3 Annex 3 - General population exposure estimates

Average and high external exposure to BPA from all sources in the general population (ng/kg bw/day) indicated in the EFSA CEF Panel 2015 report, p.61:

"External exposure to BPA was estimated by forward exposure modelling. This involved the assessment of chronic exposure (absorbed dose) to BPA through different sources (diet, thermal paper, air, dust, toys, cosmetics) and routes of exposure (oral, inhalation and dermal) in the EU population. Analytical/experimental BPA concentrations were combined with food consumption (including human milk) to estimate dietary exposure and concentration data in and from non-food sources with behaviour patterns to estimate non-dietary exposure. For the oral route, an overall external exposure estimate was derived by adding up the average estimates from different

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sources. For dermal exposures, direct addition is not appropriate, as absorption depends on the source. For high external exposure, the same procedure was followed".

Table 12: Average and high external exposure estimates to BPA from all sources in the general population (ng/kg bw per day) according to EFSA CEF Panel 2015 report

	Average (A) or high (H) external exposure	Ingestion	Inhalation	Dermal	Total	Contribution of ingestion to BPA total exposure	Contribution of inhalation to BPA total exposure	Contribution of dermal to BPA total exposure
Infants 1-5 days (breastfed)	A	225	0,7	-	225,7	99,7%	0,3%	0,0%
	H	435	1,4	-	436,4	99,7%	0,3%	0,0%
Infants 6 days - 3 months (breastfed)	A	174	0,7	4,8	179,5	96,9%	0,4%	2,7%
	H	615	1,4	9,4	625,8	98,3%	0,2%	1,5%
Infants 4-6 months (breastfed)	A	154	0,7	4,8	159,5	96,6%	0,4%	3,0%
	H	543	1,4	9,4	553,8	98,0%	0,2%	1,7%
Infants 0-6 months (formula fed)	A	39	0,7	4,8	44,5	87,6%	1,6%	10,8%
	H	95	1,4	9,4	105,8	89,8%	1,3%	8,9%
Infants 6-12 months	A	384	0,7	4,8	389,5	98,6%	0,2%	1,2%
	H	872	1,4	9,4	882,8	98,8%	0,2%	1,1%
Toddlers 1-3 years	A	382	0,7	2,8	385,5	99,1%	0,2%	0,7%
	H	869	1,1	5,5	875,6	99,2%	0,1%	0,6%
Children 3-10 years	A	293	0,4	71	364,4	80,4%	0,1%	19,5%
	H	818	0,6	554,2	1372,8	59,6%	0,0%	40,4%
Adolescents 10-18 years	A	161	0,4	96,3	257,7	62,5%	0,2%	37,4%
	H	384	0,6	867,8	1252,4	30,7%	0,0%	69,3%
Women 18-45 years	A	133	0,2	60,9	194,1	68,5%	0,1%	31,4%
	H	389	0,3	546	935,3	41,6%	0,0%	58,4%
Men 18-45 years	A	127	0,2	60,9	188,1	67,5%	0,1%	32,4%
	H	336	0,3	546	882,3	38,1%	0,0%	61,9%
Other adults 45-65 years	A	127	0,2	60,9	188,1	67,5%	0,1%	32,4%
	H	342	0,3	546	888,3	38,5%	0,0%	61,5%
Elderly & very elderly >=65 years	A	117	0,2	60,9	178,1	65,7%	0,1%	34,2%
	H	376	0,3	546	922,3	40,8%	0,0%	59,2%

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From the average and high external exposure assessment to BPA from all sources in the general population, as estimated via the so-called forward modelling approach by EFSA¹³, estimations of source-specific doses reaching the physical barriers (gastro-intestinal tract, respiratory tract and skin) were calculated. Further, relative contributions of the ingestion, inhalation and dermal routes to total BPA exposure were estimated for different age-and gender-groups (see Table 12 above). By only considering the oral and dermal routes (since inhalation apparently is not a significant contributor to the overall exposure to BPA for the general population), the concentration of total BPA in urine consistent with the concentration of free BPA in plasma obtained after exposure to 4 µg/kg bw/day (t-TDI averaged over 24h) can be estimated according to variable percentage of relative contributions of the cutaneous and oral routes.

If considering for example an exposure scenario with 70% oral and 30% dermal exposure to BPA (based on average external exposure estimates for adults 18-45 years), the concentration of total BPA in urine can be estimated with the following approach:

- Concentration of total BPA in urine for an adult (70 kg) after constant oral exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over a day: 233 µg/L
- Concentration of total BPA in urine for an adult (70 kg) after constant dermal exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw averaged over a day: 6 µg/L
- Concentration of total BPA in urine for an adult (70 kg) after constant exposure to 4 µg BPA/kg bw over a day, resulting from a 70% oral and 30% dermal intake:
70% * 233 + 30% * 6 = 165 µg/L

10.4 Annex 4 - Derivation of Biomonitoring Equivalents consistent with the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day

The assumptions for bodyweight, average 24-h urinary volume and creatinine excretion for children (6-11 years), adolescents (11-16 years) and male and female adults are summarised in Table 13 (Krishnan et al., 2010).

Table 13: Assumptions for bodyweight, average 24-h urinary volume and creatinine excretion, and estimates of average volume-based and creatinine-adjusted urinary concentration of total BPA (free and conjugated species) consistent with exposure at a unit dose (1 µg/kg-d) (Krishnan et al., 2010)

Age group	Bodyweight, kg	Average 24h urinary volume, L (Creatinine excretion, g)	BPA urinary concentration, µg/L (µg/g creat) per µg/kg/day oral dose
Children, 6–11y	32	0.66 (0.5)	48.5 (64.0)
Adolescents, 11–16y	57	1.65 (1.2)	34.5 (47.5)
Men > 16y	70	1.7 (1.5)	41.2 (46.7)
Women > 16y	55	1.6 (1.2)	34.4 (45.8)
Average, µg/L (µg/g creat)			39.6 (51.0)

¹³ Extracted from the EFSA CEF Panel 2015 report: "Internal exposures to total BPA, as estimated by forward modelling, are in good agreement with the backward-modelling estimates obtained from urinary biomonitoring, suggesting that it is likely that no major exposure sources have been missed for the forward-modelled exposure assessment. It is, however, important to highlight the fact that the internal exposure estimation of total BPA includes conservative assumptions resulting in likely overestimation of exposure that could in theory have hidden other possible sources of exposure. The CEF Panel noted also that there are considerable uncertainties in the forward and backward estimates of internal exposure."

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Limit values for total BPA in urine, calculated by the biomonitoring equivalent approach and using an urinary mass balance equation (see HBM4EU concept document on the HBM-GV derivation methodology) are described below (adapted from Krishnan et al., 2010).

Table 14: Derivation of a limit value for total BPA in urine consistent with the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day

Derivation steps	Exposure guidance value (children, adolescents, men, women)	
1	POD, µg/kg bw/d	BMDL ₁₀ of 8960
2	HED _{POD} using the HEDF of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice, µg/kg/d	609
	AF (TD component of interspecies differences)	2.5
	Adjusted HED _{POD} , µg/kg/d	244
3	Total BPA concentration in urine per unit dose (average of children, adolescents, men, women):	
	µg/L per µg/kg/d	39,6
	µg/g creatinine per µg/kg/d	51
4	BE _{POD} :	
	µg/L	9662
	µg/g creatinine	12444
4	AF _H x AF _{database} : 10 x 6	60
	HBM-GV (for total BPA in urine):	
	µg/L	161
	µg/g creatinine	207

Derivation steps	Exposure guidance value (Men > 16y; bw=70kg)	
1	POD, µg/kg bw/d	BMDL ₁₀ of 8960
2	HED _{POD} using the HEDF of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice, µg/kg/d	609
	AF (TD component of interspecies differences)	2.5
	Adjusted HED _{POD} , µg/kg/d	244
3	Total BPA concentration in urine per unit dose (men > 16y):	
	µg/L per µg/kg/d	41.2
	µg/g creatinine per µg/kg/d	46.7
4	BE _{POD} :	
	µg/L	10053
	µg/g creatinine	11395
4	AF _H x AF _{database} : 10 x 6	60
	HBM-GV (for total BPA in urine):	
	µg/L	168
	µg/g creatinine	190

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Derivation steps	Exposure guidance value (Women > 16y; bw=55kg)	
1	POD, µg/kg bw/d	BMDL ₁₀ of 8960
2	HED _{POD} using the HEDF of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice, µg/kg/d	609
	AF (TD component of interspecies differences)	2.5
	Adjusted HED _{POD} , µg/kg/d	244
3	Total BPA concentration in urine per unit dose (women > 16y) µg/L per µg/kg/d µg/g creatinine per µg/kg/d	34.4 45.8
	BE _{POD} : µg/L µg/g creatinine	8394 11175
4	AF _H x AF _{database} : 10 x 6	60
	HBM-GV (for total BPA in urine): µg/L µg/g creatinine	140 186

Derivation steps	Exposure guidance value (Children 6-11y; bw=32kg)	
1	POD, µg/kg bw/d	BMDL ₁₀ of 8960
2	HED _{POD} using the HEDF of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice, µg/kg/d	609
	AF (TD component of interspecies differences)	2.5
	Adjusted HED _{POD} , µg/kg/d	244
3	Total BPA concentration in urine per unit dose (child 6-11y) µg/L per µg/kg/d µg/g creatinine per µg/kg/d	48.5 64.0
	BE _{POD} : µg/L µg/g creatinine	11834 15616
4	AF _H x AF _{database} : 10 x 6	60
	HBM-GV (for total BPA in urine): µg/L µg/g creatinine	197 260

10.5 Annex 5 - Simulations for a BPA constant but discontinuous dermal exposure over 5 days corresponding to an occupational exposure scenario

A constant 24h-averaged exposure to 4 µg/kg bw of BPA (TDI from EFSA, 2015) by oral intake for an adult from the general population (men 45 years, 70 kg) leads to a free BPA plasmatic concentration of 6.8 ng/L according to the selected PBPK model. Simulation of a discontinuous dermal exposure over a working week was performed by setting this threshold value as the maximum value retrieved after 8h exposure per day over 5 consecutive days (i.e. as if the sampling was performed end of the working shift and week). Figure 9 shows the variation of the

plasmatic total and free BPA concentrations, whereas Figure 10 shows the variation of urinary total and free BPA concentrations over the 5 days.

Figure 9: Estimated plasmatic total and free BPA concentrations (nmol/L) for a 70 kg adult after a constant but discontinuous dermal exposure (8h/day over 5 consecutive days) generating the same concentration of free BPA in plasma at the end of workshift and working week than a 100% oral intake of 4 µg/kg bw averaged over 24h

Figure 10: Estimated urinary total and free BPA concentrations (nmol/L) for a 70 kg adult after a constant but discontinuous dermal exposure (8h/day over 5 consecutive days) generating the same concentration of free BPA in plasma at the end of workshift and working week than a 100% oral intake of 4 µg/kg bw averaged over 24h

The predicted urinary concentration of total BPA at the end of the working shift and week is 5.7 µg/L (25 nmol/L).

10.6 Annex 6 - Biomonitoring studies on occupational exposure to BPA

Table15: Biomonitoring studies on occupational exposure to BPA (adapted from Heinälä et al., 2017)

Total urinary BPA concentration, µg/L (µg/g creatinine)							
Occupation	Number of participants (sampling time)	AM ± SD	GM ± GSD	Median	P75	Range	Ref
Plastic injection molding factory	70 (post-shift)	-	3.88	3.88 ± 2.65	4.99		Kouidhi et al. (2017)
Manufacturing phenolic resin	28 (pre-shift) 158 (mid-shift through Day 2 end-shift)		6.56 (2.90) 33.8 (4.68)			0.78–112 1.15–1230	Hines et al. (2017)
Manufacturing epoxy resins	191 (post-shift)	(5580)	-	(108)	(870)	-	He et al. (2009)
Manufacturing BPA	7 (post-shift)	(543)	-	(233) ^a	(232) ^a	-	He et al. (2009)
Manufacturing BPA	7 (pre-shift) 42 (mid-shift through Day 2 end-shift)		37.4 (4.01) 121 (9.36)			9.94–441 11.5–18900	Hines et al. (2017)
Manufacturing epoxy resins and BPA	123 (pre-shift)	-	-	(57.9)	(467)	-	Li et al. (2010b)
Manufacturing polycarbonate resins and BPA	18 (pre-shift) 104 (mid-shift through Day 2 end-shift)		69.4 (4.12) 218 (3.41)			6.56–553 17.8–4720	Hines et al. (2017)
Manufacturing epoxy resins	28 (post-shift)	-	55.73 ± 5.48 (31.96 ± 4.42)	48.06 (21.42)	164.52 (111.86)	5.56– 1934.85 (4.61– 1253.69)	Wang et al. (2012)
Manufacturing BPA	91 (post-shift)	-	-	-	(2062) (max)		Brill et al. (2013)
Epoxy resin sprayers	42 (10–12 am)	-	-	(2.1)	-	(ND–22.6)	Hanaoka et al. (2002)
Epoxy resin painters	25	(2.61 ± 1.08)	-	-	-	-	Cha et al. (2008)
Manufacturing BPA-filled wax/reclaim	14 (pre-shift) 84 (mid-shift through Day 2 end-shift)		111 (4.66) 457 (4.31)			14.5–1580 22.2–5400	Hines et al. (2017)
Manufacturing BPA-filled wax, casting patterns/molds, wax melt/burnout	10 (pre-shift) 60 (mid-shift through Day 2 end-shift)		25.4 (5.14) 84.5 (5.23)			2.54–257 6.24–5790	Hines et al. (2017)
Firefighters	101	-	1.58 (1.40)	1.53 (1.25)	3.16 (2.03)	37.4 (21.1) (max)	Waldman et al. (2016)
Cashiers	17	-	(2.8 ± 1.1)	-	-	—	Braun et al. (2011)

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Total urinary BPA concentration, µg/L (µg/g creatinine)							
Occupation	Number of participants (sampling time)	AM ± SD	GM ± GSD	Median	P75	Range	Ref
Cashiers	33 (post-shift)	-	(2.76 ± 3.53)	-	-	(0.44–187.96)	Thayer et al. (2016)
Cashiers	90 (various)	20.2 (12.0)	8.58 ± 2.83 (7.10 ± 2.30)	8.92 (6.76)	-	0.54–1915 (0.68–704)	Ndaw et al. (2016)

AM, arithmetic mean; GM, geometric mean; GSD, geometric mean standard deviation; ND, not detected; SD, standard deviation.

^a **Either the median or the 75th percentile must be incorrect because the 75th percentile cannot be smaller than the median. Unfortunately, the original authors could no longer determine which was the correct value (He Y, personal communication).**

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- Almeida, S., Raposo, A., Almeida-González, M. and Carrascosa, C. (2018), Bisphenol A: Food Exposure and Impact on Human Health. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*.
- Alonso-Magdalena P, García-Arévalo M, Quesada I, Nadal Á, 2015. Bisphenol-a treatment during pregnancy in mice: a new window of susceptibility for the development of diabetes in mothers later in life. *Endocrinology*, 156(5):1659–1670.
- Andra, S.S., Austin, C, Yang, J., Patel, D., Arora, M., 2016. Recent advances in simultaneous analysis of bisphenol A and its conjugates in human matrices: exposure biomarker perspectives. *Sci. Total Environ*, 572, pp. 770-781. Available at: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.062](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.062)
- Angle BM, Do RP, Ponzi D, Stahlhut RW, Drury BE, Nagel SC, Welshons WV, Besch-Williford CL, Palanza P, Parmigiani S, vom Saal FS, Taylor JA., 2013. Metabolic disruption in male mice due to fetal exposure to low but not high doses of bisphenol A (BPA): evidence for effects on body weight, food intake, adipocytes, leptin, adiponectin, insulin and glucose regulation. *Reprod Toxicol*, 42: 256-68.
- ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), 2011. Usages du bisphenol A. Saisine No. 2010-SA-0197. Rapport d'étude. Rapport septembre 2011 avec erratum de novembre 2011. ANSES, Paris, 68p. Available at: <http://www.anses.fr/Documents/CHIM-Ra-BisphenolA.pdf>
- ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), 2013. Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on the assessment of the risks associated with bisphenol A for human health, and on toxicological data and data on the use of bisphenols S, F, M, B, AP, AF and BADGE. Available at: <https://www.anses.fr/en/system/files/CHIM2009sa0331Ra-0EN.PDF>. Scientific appraisal report (in french) available at: <https://www.anses.fr/en/system/files/CHIM2009sa0331Ra-1.pdf>
- ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), 2014. Annex XV restriction report - Proposal for a restriction, substance name: 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (bisphenol A; BPA). Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/c6a8003c-81f3-4df6-b7e8-15a3a36baf76>
- ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), 2017. Annex XV Report. Proposal for Identification of a Substance of Very High Concern on the Basis of the Criteria Set Out in REACH Article 57. Substance Name(s): 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (Bisphenol a). EC Number: 201-245-8. CAS Number: 80-05-7. Submitted by: France. Date: 02/03/2017. <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/93bf4be3-9af6-d7ca-8b07-4e8fb42bad11>
- Apel P, Angerer J, Wilhelm M, Kolossa-Gehring M, 2017. New HBM values for emerging substances, inventory of reference and HBM values in force and working principles of the German Human Biomonitoring Commission. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.09.007>
- Arcadis, 2013. Inventarisation of the use of bisphenol A at the working place and investigation of the risks of BPA substitutes, Final report, Project number BE0113000442, version 3, 29-11-2013.
- Ashford RD., 1994. *Ashford's Dictionary of Industrial Chemicals*, Wavelength Publications Ltd., London, England.

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- Balakrishnan B, Henare K, Thorstensen EB, Ponnampalam AP, Mitchell MD, 2010. Transfer of bisphenol A across the human placenta, *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, Volume 202, Issue 4, 2010, Pages 393.e1-393.e7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2010.01.025>.
- Becker K, Göen T, Seiwert M, Conrad A, Pick-Fuss H, Müller J, Wittassek M, Schulz C, Kolossa-Gehring M., 2009. GerES IV: phthalate metabolites and bisphenol A in urine of German children. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*;212(6):685-92. Bernier MR, Vandenberg LN., 2017. Handling of thermal paper: Implications for dermal exposure to bisphenol A and its alternatives. *PLoS ONE* 12(6): e0178449. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178449>
- Betancourt AM, Eltoum IA, Desmond RA, Russo J, Lamartiniere CA., 2010. In utero exposure to bisphenol A shifts the window of susceptibility for mammary carcinogenesis in the rat. *Environ Health Perspect* 118(11): 1614-1619.
- Beausoleil C, Emond C, Cravedi JP, Antignac JP, Applanat M, et al. 2018. Regulatory identification of BPA as an endocrine disruptor: Context and methodology. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, Elsevier, 2018, 475, pp.4-9.
- Berman T, Goldsmith R, Göen T, Spungen J, Novack L, Levine H, Amitai Y, Shohat T, Grotto I, 2014. Demographic and dietary predictors of urinary bisphenol A concentrations in adults in Israel. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, Volume 217, Issue 6, p638-644.
- Biedermann, S., Tschudin, P., Grob, K., 2010. Transfer of bisphenol a from thermal printer paper to the skin. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 398:571–576. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-010-3936-9>.
- Boucher JG, Boudreau A, Ahmed S, Atlas E., 2015. In vitro effects of bisphenol A β -D-Glucuronide (BPA-G) on adipogenesis in human and murine preadipocytes. *Environ Health Perspect* 123(12):1287–1293.
- Braun, J.M., Kalkbrenner, A.E., Calafat, A.M., et al., 2011. Variability and predictors of urinary bisphenol A concentrations during pregnancy. *Environ Health Perspect* ; 119, 131–37.
- Brill, S., Bader, M., Becker, K., et al. 2013. Biomonitoring of employees occupationally exposed to bisphenol A - a comparison with environmental and occupational assessment values. The 9th international Symposium on Biological Monitoring in Occupational and Environmental Health, Manchester, England.
- Buscher B, van de Lagemaat D., Gries W., Beyer D., Markham D.A., Budinsky R.A., Dimond S.S., Nath R.V., Snyder S.A., Hentges S.G., 2015. Quantitative analysis of unconjugated and total bisphenol A in human urine using solid-phase extraction and UPLC-MS/MS: method implementation, method qualification and troubleshooting *J. Chromatogr. B*, 1005, pp. 30-38.
- Calafat, A. M., Ye, X., Wong, L.-Y., Reidy, J. A. & Needham, L. L., 2007. Exposure of the U.S. Population to Bisphenol A and 4-tertiary-Octylphenol: 2003–2004. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 116, 39–44.
- Caporossi, L., & Papaleo, B., 2015. Exposure to bisphenol A and gender differences: From rodents to humans evidences and hypothesis about the health effects. *Journal of Xenobiotics*, 5(1), 15–19.
- Carr RL, Bertasi FR, Betancourt AM, Bowers SD, Gandy BS, Ryan PL, Willard ST., 2003. Effect of neonatal rat bisphenol A exposure on performance in the Morris water maze. *J Tox Environ Health Part A* 66: 2077-2088.
- Casas M, Valvi D, Luque N, Ballesteros-Gomez A, Carsin AE, Fernandez MF, Koch HM, Mendez MA, Sunyer J, Rubio S, Vrijheid M., 2013. Dietary and sociodemographic determinants of

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bisphenol A urine concentrations in pregnant women and children. *Environ Int.* 2013 Jun;56:10-8. Cha, B.S., Koh, S.B., Park, J.H. et al., 2008. Influence of occupational exposure to bisphenol A on the sex hormones of male epoxy resin painters. *Mol Cell Toxicol*, 4: 230–4.

Chao Y, Chen J, Yang W, Ho T, Yen F., 2015. Exposure Hazard to Bisphenol A for Labor and Particle Size Distribution at Polycarbonate Molding Plants. *Iran J Public Health*; 44(6):783-90.

Chemical Watch, 2011. France votes to Ban BPA in Food Contact Materials.

<https://chemicalwatch.com/8667/france-votes-to-ban-bpa-in-food-contact-materials> (Accessed 7 August 2018).

Chung YH, Han JH, Lee SB, Lee YH. Inhalation Toxicity of Bisphenol A and Its Effect on Estrous Cycle, Spatial Learning, and Memory in Rats upon Whole-Body Exposure. *Toxicol Res* 2017; 33(2): 165-71.

Corbel, T. et al., 2013. Bisphenol A disposition in the sheep maternal-placental-fetal unit: mechanisms determining fetal internal exposure. *Biol. Reprod.* 89, 11.

Covaci, A. *et al.* 2015. Urinary BPA measurements in children and mothers from six European member states: Overall results and determinants of exposure. *Environ. Res.* 141, 77–85.

Commission Directive 2011/8/EU of 28 January 2011, amending Directive 2002/72/EC as regards the restriction of use of Bisphenol A in plastic infant feeding bottles. Official Journal of the European Union. L 26/11. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2011:026:0011:0014:EN:PDF>

Commission Directive (EU) 2017/898 of 24 May 2017 amending, for the purpose of adopting specific limit values for chemicals used in toys, Appendix C to Annex II to Directive 2009/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the safety of toys, as regards bisphenol A. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017L0898&from=EN>

Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/1179 of 19 July 2016 amending, for the purposes of its adaptation to technical and scientific progress, Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures. Official Journal of the European Union. L195/11. Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.195.01.0011.01.ENG

Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/2235 of 12 December 2016 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) as regards bisphenol A. Official Journal of the European Union. L 337/3. Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.337.01.0003.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2016:337:TOC

Commission Regulation 2018/213/EU of 12 February 2018 on the use of bisphenol A in varnishes and coatings intended to come into contact with food, amending Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 as regards the use of that substance in plastic food contact materials. Official Journal of the European Union. L 41/6. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018R0213>

Corrales J, Kristofco LA, Steele WB, Yates BS, Breed CS, Williams ES, Brooks BW, 2015. Global Assessment of Bisphenol A in the Environment: Review and Analysis of Its Occurrence and Bioaccumulation. *Dose Response*. 13(3):1559325815598308.

Cousins IT, Staples CA, Klecka GM and Mackay D, 2002. A multimedia assessment of the environmental fate of bisphenol A. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment*, 8, 1107–1135.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
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Available at:

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1a76/582ed0d720cccd99bac30c0859a4898f3933.pdf>

- Csanády G., Oberste-Frielinghaus H., Semder B., Baur C., Schneider K., and Filser J., 2002. Distribution and unspecific protein binding of the xenoestrogens bisphenol A and daidzein. *Archives of Toxicology*, vol. 76, no. 5-6, pp. 299–305.
- Danish EPA, 2012. Exposure of pregnant consumers to suspected endocrine disruptors. Available at: <https://www2.mst.dk/Udgiv/publications/2012/04/978-87-92903-02-0.pdf>
- Deceuninck Y, Bichon E, Durand S, Bemrah-Aouachria N, Zengong Z, Morvan ML, Marchand P, Dervilly-Pinel G, Antignac JP, Leblanc JC, Le Bizec B. Development and validation of a MIP/GC-MS/MS method for the determination of bisphenol A residues in wide range of food items. *Journal of Chromatography A* 2014;1362: 241-249.
- Delclos KB et al., 2014. Toxicity evaluation of bisphenol A administered by gavage to Sprague Dawley rats from gestation day 6 through postnatal day 90. *Toxicol Sci*, 139(1):174-97.
- Demierre A-L, Peter R, Oberli A, Bourqui-Pittet M., 2012. Dermal penetration of bisphenol A in human skin contributes marginally to total exposure. *Toxicol Lett* 213(3):305–308.
- Dereumeaux C, Fillol C, Charles MA, Denys S, 2017. The French Human Biomonitoring program: First lessons from the perinatal component and future needs, *Int. Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, Vol 220, Issue 2, Part A, 2017, Pages 64-70.
- DFG, 1996 (updated in 2011). The MAK Value Documentation for BPA, the MAK-Collection Part I. Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/3527600418.mb8005e5014>
- Divakaran, K., Hines, R.N., McCarver, D.G., 2014. Human hepatic UGT2B15 developmental expression. *Toxicol. Sci.* 141:292–299. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfu126>.
- Dodds, E. C., Lawson, W., 1938. Molecular structure in relation to oestrogenic activity. Compounds without a phenanthrene nucleus. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B* 125, 222–232.
doi:10.1098/rspb.1938.0023
- Dodds, E. C., Goldberg, L., Lawson, W., Robinson, R., 1938. Estrogenic activity of certain synthetic compounds. *Nature* 141, 247–248. [doi:10.1038/141247b0](https://doi.org/10.1038/141247b0)
- Doerge DR, Twaddle NC, Vanlandingham M, Fisher JW., 2010a. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in neonatal and adult Sprague-Dawley rats. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 247:158–65.
- Doerge DR, Twaddle NC, Woodling KA, Fisher JW., 2010b. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in neonatal and adult rhesus monkeys. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 248:1–11.
- Doerge DR, Vanlandingham M, Twaddle NC, Delclos KB., 2010c. Lactational transfer of bisphenol A in Sprague-Dawley rats. *ToxicolLett* 199:372–6.
- Doerge DR, Twaddle NC, Vanlandingham M, Fisher JW. 2011a. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in neonatal and adult CD-1 mice: inter-species comparisons with Sprague-Dawley rats and rhesus monkeys. *Toxicol Lett* 207:298–305.
- Doerge, D.R., Twaddle, N.C., Vanlandingham, M., Brown, R.P., Fisher, J.W., 2011b. Distribution of bisphenol A in to tissues of adult, neonatal, and fetal Sprague–Dawley rats. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 255(3):261–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2011.07.009>
- Doerge DR, Twaddle NC, Vanlandingham M and Fisher JW, 2012. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in serum and adipose tissue following intravenous administration to adult female CD-1 mice. *Toxicology Letters*, 211, 114-119.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
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- Draganov D.I., Markham D.A., Beyer D., Waechter J.M., Dimond S.S., Budinsky R.A., Shiotsuka R.N., Snyder S.A., Ehman K.D., Hentges S.G., 2015. Extensive metabolism and route-dependent pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A (BPA) in neonatal mice following oral or subcutaneous administration *Toxicology*, 333, pp. 168-178.
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), 2015. Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC) and Committee for Socio-economic Analysis (SEAC) background document to the Opinion on the Annex XV dossier proposing restrictions on 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (Bisphenol A; BPA). Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/d52d2c6b-2f1c-4ddf-bb44-4e3e42ea1820>
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), 2017a. Inclusion of substances of very high concern in the Candidate List for eventual inclusion in Annex XIV. Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/36834f25-582c-0855-37fb-bd20b409382c>
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), 2017b. Agreement of the Member States Committee on the Identification of 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (bisphenol A) as a Substance of Very high Concern. Available at: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/23665416/svhc_msc_agreement_bpa_20170614_11847_en.pdf/3321860d-daad-06b3-3b32-b633ce1d9cde
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), 2018a. Market Survey: Use of bisphenol A and its alternatives in thermal paper in the EU from 2014 to 2017. Available at: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/22863068/bpa_in_thermal_paper_report_en.pdf/0d93cd76-345e-2ed4-698f-a3beaea6d755
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), 2018b. Inclusion of substances of very high concern in the Candidate List for eventual inclusion in Annex XIV. Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/ede153a4-db00-daf6-120f-6b6ccce0c539>
- Edlow, A.G., Chen, M., Smith, N.A., Lu, C., McElrath, T.F., 2012. Fetal bisphenol A exposure: concentration of conjugated and unconjugated bisphenol A in amniotic fluid in the second and third trimesters. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 34:1–7.
- Edginton, A.N., Ritter, L., 2009. Predicting plasma concentrations of bisphenol A in children younger than 2 years of age after typical feeding schedules, using a physiologically based toxicokinetic model. *Environ Health Perspect.* 117(4):645-52. doi: 10.1289/ehp.0800073. Epub 2008 Nov 14.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Opinion of the Scientific Panel on Food Additives, Flavourings, Processing Aids and Materials in Contact with Food on a request from the Commission related to 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl) propane (Bisphenol A). Question number EFSA-Q-2005-100. *EFSA Journal* 2006; 428:1–75. Available at: <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/fr/scdocs/scdoc/428.htm>
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2008. Scientific Opinion of the Panel on Food Additives, Flavourings, Processing aids and Materials in Contact with Food (AFC) on a request from the Commission on the toxicokinetics of Bisphenol A. *The EFSA Journal*, 2008, 759, 1-10 pp.
- EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials Enzymes Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2010. Scientific Opinion on bisphenol A: evaluation of a study investigating its neurodevelopmental toxicity, review of recent scientific literature on its toxicity and advice on the Danish riskassessment of bisphenol A. *EFSA Journal* 2010; 8(9):1829, 110 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1829.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 73

- EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials Enzymes Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2011. Statement on the ANSES reports on bisphenol A. *EFSA Journal* 2011; 9(12):2475, 10 pp.doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2475.
- EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2015. Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs: executive summary. *EFSA Journal*. 2015; 13 (1), 3978.
- EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2016. A statement on the developmental immunotoxicity of bisphenol A (BPA): answer to the question from the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport. *EFSA Journal* 2016; 14(10):4580, 22 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2016.4580.
- Ehrlich S, Calafat AM, Humblet O et al. (2014) Handling of thermal receipts as a source of exposure to bisphenol A. *JAMA*; 311: 859–60.
- Ema M, Fujii S, Furukawa M, Kiguchi M, Ikka T, Harazono A., 2001. Rat two-generation reproductive toxicity study of bisphenol A. *Reprod Toxicol*, 15(5):505-23.
- EPC (Epoxy Resin Committee). Assessment of Potential BPA Emissions in Key Applications of Epoxy Resins.
- EU, 2010. Updated European Union Risk Assessment Report. Bisphenol a, CAS No: 80-05-7. Institute for Health and Consumer Protection. European Chemicals Bureau, European Commission Joint Research Centre, 3rd Priority List, Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- EU RAR (European Union Risk assessment report) for 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol (bisphenol A), 2003. Available at: <https://oehha.ca.gov/media/downloads/crn/eubisphenolareport325.pdf>
- EU RAR (European Union Risk assessment report), 2008.Updated European Risk Assessment Report for 4,4'- isopropylidenediphenol (Bisphenol-A).
- Fan, R., Zeng, B., Liu, X., Chen, C., Zhuang, Q., Wang, Y., Hu, M., Lv, Y., Li, J., Zhou, Y., et al., 2015. Levels of bisphenol-A in different paper products in Guangzhou, China, and assessment of human exposure via dermal contact. *Environ. Sci. Process. Impacts*, 17, 667–673.
- FAO/WHO (Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations and World Health Organisation), 2011. Joint FAO/WHO Expert Meeting to review toxicological and health aspects of Bisphenol A. 60 pp.
- Fisher JW, Twaddle NC, Vanlandingham M and Doerge DR, 2011. Pharmacokinetic modeling: prediction and evaluation of route dependent dosimetry of bisphenol A in monkeys with extrapolation to humans. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 257, 122-136.
- FOPH (Federal Office of Public Health) (2016). Bisphenol A. Factsheet. February 2016. FOPH of the Swiss Confederation. <https://www.bag.admin.ch/dam/bag/fr/dokumente/chem/themen-a-z/factsheetbisphenol-a.pdf.download.pdf/2016-bpa-factsheet->
- Fox, S.D., et al., 2011. Quantitation of free and total bisphenol A in human urine using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *J. Sep. Sci.* 34 (11), 1268–1274.
- Frederiksen H., Nielsen J.K., Mørck T.A., Hansen P.W., Jensen J.F., Nielsen O., Andersson A.M. & Knudsen L.E., 2013. Urinary excretion of phthalate metabolites, phenols and parabens in rural and urban Danish mother– child pairs. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 216 772–783. doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.02.006
- Frederiksen H, Jensen TK, Jørgensen N, Kyhl HB, Husby S, Skakkebæk NE, Main KM, Juul A, Andersson AM., 2014. Human urinary excretion of non-persistent environmental chemicals: an

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 74

overview of Danish data collected between 2006 and 2012. *Reproduction*. 147(4):555-65. doi: 10.1530/REP-13-0522. Galloway T, Cipelli R, Guralnik J, Ferrucci L, Bandinelli S, Corsi AM, Money C, McCormack P, Melzer D., 2010. Daily bisphenol A excretion and associations with sex hormone concentrations: results from the InCHIANTI adult population study. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2010 Nov;118(11):1603-8.

García-Arévalo M, Alonso-Magdalena P, Servitja JM, Boronat-Belda T, Merino B, Villar-Pazos S, Medina-Gómez G, Novials A, Quesada I, Nadal A, 2016. Maternal Exposure to Bisphenol-A During Pregnancy Increases Pancreatic β -Cell Growth During Early Life in Male Mice Offspring, *Endocrinology*, Volume 157, Issue 11, 4158–4171.

Gauderat, G. *et al.* 2016. Bisphenol A glucuronide deconjugation is a determining factor of fetal exposure to bisphenol A. *86*, 52–59.

Gauderat, G., Picard-Hagen, N., Toutain P-L, Servien, R., Vigié, C., Puel, S., Lacroix, M.Z., Corbel, T., Bousquet-Melou, A., Gayrard, V., 2017. Prediction of human prenatal exposure to bisphenol A and bisphenol A glucuronide from an ovine semi-physiological toxicokinetic model. *Sci Rep*. 7: 15330.

Gayrard V, Lacroix M, Collet S, Bousquet-Melou A, Toutain P.L. & Picard-Hagen N., 2013. High bioavailability of bisphenol A from sublingual exposure. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 121, 951–956.

Geens, T., Roosens, L., Neels, H., Covaci, A., 2009. Assessment of human exposure to Bisphenol-A, Triclosan and Tetrabromobisphenol-A through indoor dust intake in Belgium. *Chemosphere*, 76, 755–760.

Geens, T., Goeyens, L., Covaci, A., 2011. Are potential sources for human exposure to bisphenol-A overlooked? *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 214, 339–347.

Geens, T., Aerts, D., Berthot, C., Bourguignon, J.P., Goeyens, L., Lecomte, P., Maghuin-Rogister, G., Pironnet, A.M., Pussemier, L., Scippo, M.L., et al., 2012. A review of dietary and non-dietary exposure to bisphenol-A. *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 50, 3725–3740.

Genius S.J., Beesoon S., Birkholz D., Lobo R.A., 2011. Human excretion of bisphenol A: blood, urine, and sweat BUS study, *Environ. Publ. Health*, 185731.

Giesbrecht, G. F., Ejaredar, M., Liu, J., Thomas, J., Letourneau, N., Campbell, T., Martin, J. W., Dewey, D., 2017. Prenatal bisphenol A exposure and dysregulation of infant hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis function: findings from the APrON cohort study. *Environmental Health*, 16:47.

Ginsberg, G., Rice, D.C., 2009. Does rapid metabolism ensure negligible risk from bisphenol A? *Environ. Health Perspect*. 117 (11), 1639–1643.

Gundert-Remy, U., Mielke, H., Bernauer, U., 2013. Commentary: dermal penetration of bisphenol A - consequences for risk assessment. *Toxicol. Lett.* 217:159–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2012.12.009>.

Haines, D. A. & Murray, J., 2012. Human Biomonitoring of environmental chemicals—early results of the 2007–2009 Canadian Health Measures Survey for males and females. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 215, 133–137.

Hanaoka, T., Kawamura, N., Hara, K. et al. 2002. Urinary bisphenol A and plasma hormone concentrations in male workers exposed to bisphenol A diglycidyl ether and mixed organic solvents. *Occup Environ Med*; 59: 625–8.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
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- Hanioka N, Naito T, Narimatsu S., 2008. Human UDP-glucuronosyltransferase isoforms involved in bisphenol A glucuronidation. *Chemosphere* 74, 33-36.
- Hartmann C., Uhl M., Weiss S., Koch H.M., Scharf S., König J., 2015. Human Biomonitoring of phthalate exposure in Austrian children and adults and cumulative risk assessment. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health*, 218, 489-499.
- Hauck, Z.Z., et al., 2016. Determination of bisphenol A-glucuronide in human urine using ultrahigh-pressure liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 30 (3), 400–406.
- He, Y., Miao, M., Wu, C., Yuan, W., Gao, E., Zhou, Z., Li, D.K., 2009. Occupational exposure levels of Bisphenol a among Chinese workers. *J. Occup. Health*, 51, 432–436.
- Health Canada, 2008a. Health Risk Assessment of Bisphenol A from Food Packaging Applications. Available at: https://www.canada.ca/content/dam/hc-sc/migration/hc-sc/fn-an/alt_formats/hpfb-dgpsa/pdf/securit/bpa_hra-ers-eng.pdf
- Health Canada, 2008b. Proposed risk management approach for Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis (bisphenol A). Available at: <https://www.ec.gc.ca/eseees/default.asp?lang=En&n=6FA54372-1>
- Health Council of the Netherlands. Bisphenol A. Health-based recommendation on occupational exposure limits The Hague: Health Council of the Netherlands, 2019; publication no. 2019/04. Available at: <https://www.healthcouncil.nl/documents/advisory-reports/2019/03/26/bisphenol-a>
- Hehn, R.S., 2016. NHANES data support link between handling of thermal paper receipts and increased urinary bisphenol A excretion. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 397–404.
- Heinäälä, M., Ylinen, K., Tuomi, T., Santonen, T., Porras, S.P., 2017. Assessment of Occupational Exposure to Bisphenol A in Five Different Production Companies in Finland. *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, Volume 61, Issue 1, 1, Pages 44–55.
- Hines, C.J., Jackson, M.V., Deddens, J.A., Clark, J.C., Ye, X., Christianson, A.L., Meadows, J.W., (...), Calafat, A.M., 2017a. Urinary Bisphenol A (BPA) concentrations among workers in industries that manufacture and use BPA in the USA. *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, 61 (2), pp. 164-182.
- Hines CJ, Jackson MV, Christianson AL et al., 2017b. Air, hand wipe, and surface wipe sampling for Bisphenol A (BPA) among workers in industries that manufacture and use BPA in the United States. *J Occup Environ Hyg*; 14: 882–97.
- Hines, C.J. Christianson, A.L., Jackson M.V., Ye, X., Pretty, J.R., Arnold, J.E., Calafat, A.M, 2018. An Evaluation of the Relationship among Urine, Air, and Hand Measures of Exposure to Bisphenol A (BPA) in US Manufacturing Workers, *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, Volume 62, Issue 7, p840–851, <https://doi.org/10.1093/annweh/wxy042>
- Hormann, A.M., Vom Saal, F.S., Nagel, S.C., Stahlhut, R.W., Moyer, C.L., Ellersieck, M.R., et al., 2014. Holding thermal receipt paper and eating food after using hand sanitizer results in high serum bioactive and urine total levels of bispheol A (BPA). *PLoS One* 9, e110509.
- Ikezuki Y., Tsutsumi O., Takai Y., Kamei Y., Taketani Y., 2002. Determination of bisphenol A concentrations in human biological fluids reveals significant early prenatal exposure. *Hum. Reprod. Oxf. Engl.* 17, 2839–2841.
- INFOSAN, 2009. Bisphenol A (BPA) – Current state of knowledge and future actions by WHO and FAO. INFOSAN information note No. 5/2009 – Bisphenol A.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
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Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 76

- Jenkins S, Raghuraman N, Eltoum I, Carpenter M, Russo J, Lamartiniere CA. 2009. Oral exposure to bisphenol a increases dimethylbenzanthracene-induced mammary cancer in rats. *Environ Health Perspect* 117(6): 910-915.
- Jones, B., Watson, N., 2012. Perinatal BPA Exposure Demasculinizes Males in Measures of Affect but Has No Effect on Water Maze Learning in Adulthood. *Hormones and Behavior* 61:605–610.
- Karrer C, Roiss T, von Goetz N, Gramec Skledar D, Peterlin Mašič L, Hungerbühler K., 2018. Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Modeling of the Bisphenols BPA, BPS, BPF, and BPAF with New Experimental Metabolic Parameters: Comparing the Pharmacokinetic Behavior of BPA with Its Substitutes. *Environ Health Perspect.*;126(7):077002. doi:10.1289/EHP2739
- Karzi V, Tzatzarakis MN, Vakonaki E, et al. Biomonitoring of bisphenol A, triclosan and perfluorooctanoic acid in hair samples of children and adults, 2018. *J Appl Toxicol.* 2018 ;38:1144–1152.
- Kasper-Sonnenberg M, Wittsiepe J, Koch HM, Fromme H, Wilhelm M., 2012. Determination of bisphenol a in urine from mother-child pairs-results from the Duisburg birth cohort study, Germany. *J Toxicol Environ Health A.* 2012;75(8-10):429-37. KEMI (Swedish Chemicals Agency), 2012. Low-dose effects of Bisphenol A – identification of points of departure for the derivation of an alternative reference dose. Available at: <https://www.kemi.se/global/pm/2012/pm-8-12-bpa-low-dose-effects.pdf>
- KEMI (Swedish Chemicals Agency), 2013. Emission of Bisphenol a (BPA) from Restored Drinking Water Pipes—report from a Governmental aC. 7/13 (in Swedish). Available at: <https://www.kemi.se/en/global/rapporter/2013/rapport-7-13.pdf>
- Kim K., Park H., Yang W. & Lee J.H., 2011. Urinary concentrations of bisphenol A and triclosan and associations with demographic factors in the Korean population. *Environmental Research* 111 1280–1285.
- Koch HM, Kolossa-Gehring M, Schröter-Kermani C, Angerer J, Brüning T., 2012. Bisphenol A in 24 h urine and plasma samples of the German Environmental Specimen Bank from 1995 to 2009: a retrospective exposure evaluation. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol.* Nov;22(6):610-6.
- Kommission Human-Biomonitoring des Umweltbundesamtes, 2012. Stoffmonographie Bisphenol A (BPA) - Referenz- und Human-Biomonitoring-(HBM)-Werte für BPA im Urin. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt* 55:1215-1231. DOI 10.1007/s00103-012-1525-0. Update 2015
- Konieczna, A., Rutkowska, A., Rachoń, D., 2015. Health risk of exposure to Bisphenol A (BPA). *Rocz. Państwowego Zakładu Hig.*, 66, 5–11.
- Kortenkamp, A, Bourguignon, JP, Slama, R, Bergman, A, Demeneix, B, Ivell, R, et al., 2016. EU regulation of endocrine disruptors: a missed opportunity. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinology* 4, 649-650. Available at: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587\(16\)30151-6](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587(16)30151-6)
- Kouidhi W., Thannimalay L., Soon C. S., Ali Mohd M, 2017. Occupational exposure to bisphenol A (BPA) in a plastic injection molding factory in Malaysia. *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health*, 30(5):743-750. doi:10.13075/ijomeh.1896.00917.
- Krishnan K, Gagné M, Nong A, Aylward LL., Hays SM, 2010. Biomonitoring Equivalents for bisphenol A (BPA). *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 58, 18–24.
- Lacroix, M.Z., et al., 2011. Simultaneous quantification of bisphenol A and its glucuronide metabolite (BPA-G) in plasma and urine: applicability to toxicokinetic investigations. *Talanta* 85 (4), 2053–2059.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
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Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 77

- Le Magueresse-Battistoni B., Multigner L., Beausoleil C., Rousselle C., 2018. Effects of Bisphenol A on Metabolism and Evidences of a Mode of Action Mediated Through Endocrine Disruption. *Mol Cell Endocrinol.*;475:74-91.
- Li DK, Zhou Z, Miao M et al., 2010a. Relationship between urine bisphenol-A level and declining male sexual function. *J Androl*; 31: 500–6.
- Li, D., Zhou, Z., Qing, D., He, Y., Wu, T., Miao, M., Wang, J., Weng, X., Ferber, J.R., Herrinton, L.J., et al. 2010b. Occupational exposure to bisphenol-A (BPA) and the risk of Self-Reported Male Sexual Dysfunction. *Hum. Reprod.*, 25, 519–527.
- Li DK, Zhou Z, Miao M et al., 2011. Urine bisphenol-A (BPA) level in relation to semen quality. *Fertil Steril*; 95: 625–30e1–4.
- Liu X, Miao M, Zhou Z et al. 2015. Exposure to bisphenol-A and reproductive hormones among male adults. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol*; 39: 934–41.
- Lv Y, Lu S, Dai Y, Rui C, Wang Y, Zhou Y, Li Y, Pang Q, Fan R, 2016. Higher dermal exposure of cashiers to BPA and its association with DNA oxidative damage. *Environment International*. 98. 10.1016/j.envint.2016.10.001.
- Marquet F, Payan J-P, Beydon D et al. (2011) In vivo and ex vivo percutaneous absorption of [(14)C]-bisphenol A in rats: a possible extrapolation to human absorption? *Arch Toxicol*; 85: 1035–43.
- Martin, E. M., Fry, R. C., 2018. Environmental Influences on the Epigenome: Exposure- Associated DNA Methylation in Human Populations. *Annu. Rev. Public Health.*, 39:309–33.
- Matthews, J.B., Twomey, K., Zacharewski, T.R., 2001. In vitro and in vivo interactions of bisphenol A and its metabolite, bisphenol A glucuronide, with estrogen receptors alpha and beta. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 14 (2), 149–157.
- Mazur CS, Kenneke JF, Hess-Wilson JK, Lipscomb JC (2010). Differences between human and rat intestinal and hepatic bisphenol A glucuronidation and the influence of alamethicin on in vitro kinetic measurements. *Drug Metab Dispos* 38:2232-2238.
- McCarver DG, Hines RN, 2002. The ontogeny of human drug-metabolizing enzymes: phase II conjugation enzymes and regulatory mechanisms. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.*; 300:361–366.
- Ménard S, Guzylack-Piriou L, Leveque M, Braniste V, Lencina C, Naturel M, Moussa L, Sekkal S, Harkat C, Gaultier E, Theodorou V, Houdeau E, 2014a. Food intolerance at adulthood after perinatal exposure to the endocrine disruptor bisphenol A. *FASEB J*, 28(11):4893-900.
- Ménard S, Guzylack-Piriou L, Lencina C, Leveque M, Naturel M, Sekkal S, Harkat C, Gaultier E, Olier M, Garcia-Villar R, Theodorou V, Houdeau E, 2014b. Perinatal exposure to a low dose of bisphenol A impaired systemic cellular immune response and predisposes young rats to intestinal parasitic infection. *PLoS One*, 9(11): e112752.
- Mhaouty-Kodja S, Belzunces LP, Canivenc M-C, Schroeder H, Chevrier C, Pasquier E, 2018. Impairment of learning and memory performances induced by BPA: Evidences from the literature of a MoA mediated through an ED, *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, Vol 475, 54-73.
- Mielke H, Gundert-Remy U. 2009. Bisphenol A levels in blood depend on age and exposure. *Toxicol Lett* 190(1):32–40.
- Mielke H, Partosch F, Gundert-Remy U., 2011. The contribution of dermal exposure to the internal exposure of bisphenol A in man. *Toxicol Lett* 204(2-3):190–198.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 78

- Mielke, H., Gundert-Remy, U., 2012. Physiologically based toxicokinetic modelling as a tool to support risk assessment: three case studies. *J. Toxicol.* 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/359471>.
- Miki Y, Nakata T, Suzuki T, Darnel AD, Moriya T, Kaneko C, Hidaka K, Shiotsu Y, Kusaka H, Sasano H, 2002. Systemic distribution of steroid sulfatase and estrogen sulfotransferase in human adult and fetal tissues. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 87:5760–5768.
- Miyawaki J, Sakayama K, Kato H, Yamamoro H, Masuno H, 2007. Perinatal and postnatal exposure to bisphenol a increases adipose tissue mass and serum cholesterol level in mice. *Journal of Atherosclerosis and Thrombosis*, 14 (5): 245-252.
- Moral R, Wang R, Russo IH, Lamartiniere CA, Pereira J, Russo J., 2008. Effect of prenatal exposure to the endocrine disruptor bisphenol A on mammary gland morphology and gene expression signature. *J Endocrinol* 196: 101-112.
- Morck, T.J., Sorda, G., Bechi, N., Rasmussen, B.S., Nielsen, J.B., Ietta, F., Rytting, E., Mathiesen, L., Paulesu, L., Knudsen, L.E., 2010. Placental transport and in vitro effects of Bisphenol A. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 30:131–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2010.02.007>.
- Muna, S. Nahar, Liao, Chunyang, Kannan, Kurunthachalam, D.C.D., 2013. Fetal liver bisphenol A concentrations and biotransformation gene expression reveal variable exposure and altered capacity for metabolism in humans. *J. Biochem. Mol. Toxicol.* 27:116–123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbt>.
- Myridakis A, Fthenou E, Balaska E, Vakinti M, Kogevinas M, Stephanou EG, 2015. Phthalate esters, parabens and bisphenol-A exposure among mothers and their children in Greece (Rhea cohort). *Environ Int.* 2015 Oct;83:1-10. Nachman RM, Fox SD, Golden WC, et al., 2013. Urinary free bisphenol A and bisphenol A-glucuronide concentrations in newborns. *J Pediatr.*; 162:870–872.
- Nachman RM, Hratle JC, Lees PSJ, Groopman JD, 2014. Early Life Metabolism of Bisphenol A: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Curr Environ Health Rep.*; 1(1): 90–100.
- Ndaw, S., Remy, A., Jargot, D. et al., 2016. Occupational exposure of cashiers to bisphenol A via thermal paper: urinary biomonitoring study. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*; 89: 935–46.
- NTP (National Toxicology Program), 1982. Carcinogenesis Bioassay of Bisphenol A (CAS No. 80-05-7) in F344 Rats and B6C3F1 Mice (Feed Study). Tech Rept No TR-215.
- NTP (National Toxicology Program), 1985. Bisphenol A: reproduction and fertility assessment in CD-1 mice when administered in the feed. NTP-85-192.
- NTP-CERHR (National Toxicology Program - Center for the Evaluation of Risks to Human Reproduction), 2008. Monograph of the potential human reproductive and developmental effects of bisphenol A. Expert Panel evaluation of bisphenol A. <https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/bisphenol/bisphenol.pdf>
- Olsén L, Lampa E, Birkholz DA, Lind L, Lind PM, 2012. Circulating levels of bisphenol A (BPA) and phthalates in an elderly population in Sweden, based on the Prospective Investigation of the Vasculature in Uppsala Seniors (PIVUS), *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, Volume 75, 2012, p242-248,
- Patterson, T. A. et al., 2013. Concurrent determination of bisphenol A pharmacokinetics in maternal and fetal rhesus monkeys. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 267, 41–48.
- Philippat C, Botton J, Calafat AM, Ye X, Charles MA, Slama R; EDEN Study Group, 2014. Prenatal exposure to phenols and growth in boys. *Epidemiology*, 2014:625-35.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 79

Philippat, C., Nakiwala, D. Calafat, A. M., Botton, J., De Agostini, M., Heude, B., Slama, R., 2017. Prenatal Exposure to Nonpersistent Endocrine Disruptors and Behavior in Boys at 3 and 5 Years. *Environ Health Perspect.* 125 (9), 097014.

Plastics Europe, 2007. Applications of Bisphenol A. Available at: <http://www.bisphenol-a-europe.org/uploads/BPA%applications.Pfd>

Porras SP, Heinälä M, Santonen T, 2014. Bisphenol A exposure via thermal paper receipts, *Toxicology Letters*, Volume 230, Issue 3, p413-420.

Pottenger, L.H., et al., 2000. The relative bioavailability and metabolism of bisphenol A in rats is dependent upon the route of administration. *Toxicol. Sci.* 54 (1), 3–18.

Pouzaud F, Thierry-Mieg M, Burga K, Vérines-Jouin L, Fiore K, Beausoleil C, Michel C, Rousselle C, Pasquier E, 2018. Concerns related to ED-mediated effects of Bisphenol A and their regulatory consideration, *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, Volume 475, 2018, Pages 92-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2018.02.002>

Provencher, G., et al., 2014. Determination of bisphenol A, triclosan and their metabolites in human urine using isotope-dilution liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1348, 97–104.

Reed MJ, Purohit A, Woo LWL, Newman SP, Potter BVL., 2005. Steroid sulfatase: molecular biology, regulation, and inhibition. *Endocr Rev* 26(2):171–202.

Ribeiro, E., Ladeira, C., Viegas, S., 2017. Occupational Exposure to Bisphenol A (BPA): A Reality That Still Needs to Be Unveiled. *Toxics*, 5, 22.

Rochester JR. (2013) Bisphenol A and human health: a review of the literature. *Reprod Toxicol* 42C, 132–155.

Rochester JR, Bolden AL, Kwiatkowski CF, 2018. Prenatal exposure to bisphenol A and hyperactivity in children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Environ Int.*, 114:343-356.

RIVM (Netherlands National Institute for Public Health and the Environment), 2016. J Bakker, BC Hakkert, EVS Hessel, RJ Luit, AH Piersma, DTHM Sijm, AG Rietveld, FA van Broekhuizen, H van Loveren, JK Verhoeven 2015. Bisphenol A : Part 2. Recommendations for risk management.

Rudel RA, Camann DE, Spengler JD, Korn LR, Brody JG, 2003. Phthalates, alkylphenols, pesticides, polybrominated diphenyl ethers, and other endocrine-disrupting compounds in indoor air and dust. *Environ Sci Technol*; 37:4543–55.

Rudel, R.A., Gray, J.M., Engel, C.L., Rawsthorne, T.W., Dodson, R.E., Ackerman, J.M., Rizzo, J., Nudelman, J.L., Brody, J.G., 2011. Food packaging and bisphenol A and bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate exposure: Findings from a dietary intervention. *Environ. Health Perspect.*, 119, 914–920.

Ryan, B.C., Vandenberg, J.G., 2006. Developmental exposure to environmental estrogens alters anxiety and spatial memory in female mice. *Horm Behav* 50: 85-93.

Sarigiannis D.A, Karakitsios S.P., 2011. Perinatal exposure to Bisphenol A: the route of administration makes the dose. *Epidemiology*, 22, p. S172.

Sarigiannis, D. A., Karakitsios, S. P., Handakas, E., Simou, K., Solomou, E., Gotti, A., 2016. Integrated exposure and risk characterization of bisphenol-A in Europe. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 98,134-147.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 80

- Schönfelder G., Wittfoht W., Hopp H., Talsness C.E., Paul M., Chahoud I., 2002. Parent bisphenol A accumulation in the human maternal-fetal-placental unit. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 11011, A703–A707.
- Schöringhumer K, Cichna-Markl M. 2007. Sample clean-up with sol-gel enzyme and immunoaffinity columns for the determination of bisphenol A in human urine. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci* 850:361-369.
- SCOEL (Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit values), 2014. Recommendation from Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits for Bisphenol A.
- Sharma, R.P., Schuhmacher, M., Kumar, V., 2018. The development of a pregnancy PBPK Model for Bisphenol A and its evaluation with the available biomonitoring data. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 624, pp. 55-68.
- Shimizu M, Ohta K, Matsumoto Y, Fukuoka M, Ohno Y & Ozawa S., 2002. Sulfation of bisphenol A abolished its estrogenicity based on proliferation and gene expression in human breast cancer MCF-7 cells. *Toxicology in Vitro* 16 549–556.
- Sieli P, Jas̃arevic E, Warsak D, Mao J, Ellersieck M, Liao C, Kannan K, Collet S, Toutain P.L, vom Saal FS et al., 2011. Comparison of serum bisphenol A concentrations in mice exposed to bisphenol A through the diet versus oral bolus exposure. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 119 1260–1265.
- Snyder, R.W., Maness, S.C., Gaido, K.W., Welsch, F., Sumner, S.C.J., Fennell, T.R., 2000. Metabolism and disposition of bisphenol A in female rats. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 168(3):225–234, <https://doi.org/10.1006/taap.2000.9051>
- Søeborg, T., Frederiksen, H., Andersson, A. M., 2014. Considerations for estimating daily intake values of nonpersistent environmental endocrine disruptors based on urinary biomonitoring data. *Reproduction* (2014) 147 455–463.
- Somm E, Schwitzgebel VM, Toulotte A, Cederroth CR, Combescure C, Nef S, Aubert ML, Huppi PS., 2009. Perinatal exposure to bisphenol A alters early adipogenesis in the rat. *Environ Health Perspect* 117(10): 1549-1555.
- Song L, Xia W, Zhou Z, Li Y, Lin Y, Wei J, Wei Z, Xu B, Shen J, Li W, Xu S., 2012. Low-level phenolic estrogen pollutants impair islet morphology and β -cell function in isolated rat islets. *J Endocrinol.* 215(2):303-11.
- Sperker, B., Murdter, T.E., Schick, M., Eckhardt, K., Bosslet, K., Kroemer, H.K., 1997. Inter-individual variability in expression and activity of human betaglucuronidase in liver and kidney: consequences for drug metabolism. *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* 281, 914–920.
- SPF (Santé Publique France), 2019. Imprégnation de la population française par les bisphénols A, S et F. Programme national de biosurveillance, Esteban 2014-2016. Available at : <https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/determinants-de-sante/exposition-a-des-substances-chimiques/perturbateurs-endocriniens/documents/rapport-synthese/impregnation-de-la-population-francaise-par-les-bisphenols-a-s-et-f-programme-national-de-biosurveillance-esteban-2014-2016>
- Stahlhut R, Welshons WV & Swan S., 2009. Bisphenol A data in NHANES suggest longer than expected half-life, substantial nonfood exposure, or both. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 117 784–789.
- Staples CA, Dorn PB, Klecka GM et al., 1998. A review of the environmental fate, effects, and exposures of bisphenol A. *Chemosphere*; 36: 2149–73.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 81

- Sun Y., Irie M., Kishikawa N., Wada M., Kuroda N., Nakashima K., 2004. Determination of bisphenol A in human breast milk by HPLC with column-switching and fluorescence detection. *Biomed. Chromatogr.* 18, 501–507.
- Taylor J, vom Saal FS, Welshons WV, Drury B, Rottinghaus G, Hunt PA, Toutain P-L, Laffont C & VandeVoort C., 2011. Similarity of bisphenol A pharmacokinetics in rhesus monkeys and mice: relevance for human exposure. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 119, 422–430.
- Teeguarden, J.G., et al., 2011. Twenty-four hour human urine and serum profiles of bisphenol A during high-dietary exposure. *Toxicol. Sci.* 123 (1), 48–57.
- Teeguarden, J., Hanson-Drury, S., Fisher, J.W., Doerge, D.R., 2013. Are typical human serum BPA concentrations measurable and sufficient to be estrogenic in the general population? *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 62, 949-963.
- Teeguarden JG, Twaddle NC, Churchwell MI, Yang X, Fisher JW, Seryak LM, et al., 2015. 24-hour human urine and serum profiles of bisphenol A: evidence against sublingual absorption following ingestion in soup. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 288(2):131–142.
- Teeguarden, J. G., Twaddle, N. C., Churchwell, M. I., Doerge, D. R., 2016. Urine and serum biomonitoring of exposure to environmental estrogens I: Bisphenol A in pregnant women. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 92, 129-142.
- Tharp AP, Maffini MV, Hunt PA, Vandevort CA, Sonnenschein C, Soto AM., 2012. Bisphenol A alters the development of the rhesus monkey mammary gland. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 109(21): 8190-8195.
- Thayer, K.A., Doerge, D.R., Hunt, D., Schurman, S.H., Twaddle, N.C., Churchwell, M.I., Garantziotis, S., Kissling, G.E., Easterling, M.R., Bucher, J.R., Birnbaum, L.S., 2015a. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in humans following dermal administration. In: Teeguarden, J.G. (Ed.), *National Toxicology Program*, RTP, NC.
- Thayer, K.A., Doerge, D.R., Hunt, D., Schurman, S.H., Twaddle, N.C., Churchwell, M.I., Garantziotis, S., Kissling, G.E., Easterling, M.R., Bucher, J.R., Birnbaum, L.S., 2015b. Pharmacokinetics of bisphenol A in humans following a single oral administration. *Environ. Int.* 83, 107-115.
- Thayer, K.A., Taylor, K.W., Garantziotis, S. et al., 2016. Bisphenol A, bisphenol S, and 4-hydroxyphenyl 4-isopropoxyphenylsulfone (BPSIP) in urine and blood of cashiers. *Environ Health Perspect*; 124 : 437- 44.
- Tobacman JK, Hinkhouse M, Khalkhali-Ellis Z., 2002. Steroid sulfatase activity and expression in mammary myoepithelial cells. *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol* 81(1):65–68.
- Toner F, Allan G, Beyer D, Dimond SS, Kocabas NA. 2016. The in vitro percutaneous absorption and metabolism of Bisphenol A (BPA) through fresh human skin. *Toxicol Lett* 258 (suppl): S180.
- Toner F, Allan G, Dimond S.S, Waechter J.M, Beyer D, 2018. In vitro percutaneous absorption and metabolism of Bisphenol A (BPA) through fresh human skin, *Toxicology in Vitro*, Volume 47, 2018, Pages 147-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2017.11.002>
- Trdan Lusin T, Roskar R, Mrhar A (2012). Evaluation of bisphenol A glucuronidation according to UGT1A1*28 polymorphism by a new LC-MS/MS assay. *Toxicology* 292:33-41.
- Tsukioka T, Terasawa J, Sato S, Hatayama Y, Makino T, Nakazawa H., 2004. Development of analytical method for determining trace amounts of BPA in urine samples and estimation of exposure to BPA. *J Environ Chem* 14(1):57–63.

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 82

- Tyl RW et al., 2002. Three-generation reproductive toxicity study of dietary bisphenol A in CD Sprague-Dawley rats. *Toxicological Sciences* 68, 121-146.
- Tyl RW et al., 2008. Two-generation reproductive toxicity study of dietary bisphenol a in CD-1 (Swiss) mice. *Toxicological Sciences* 104, 362-384.
- Tzatzarakis M.N., Vakonaki E., Kavvalakis M.P., Barmpas M., Kokkinakis E.N., Xenos K., Tsatsakis A.M., 2015. Biomonitoring of bisphenol A in hair of Greek population. *Chemosphere*, 118, pp. 336-34.
- US EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency), 1993. IRIS (Integrated Risk Information System): Bisphenol A (CAS RN 80-05-7).
- US FDA (United States Food and Drug Administration), 2014. Updated safety assessment of Bisphenol A (BPA) for use in food contact applications. Memorandum. June 17, 2014. <http://www.fda.gov/downloads/NewsEvents/PublicHealthFocus/UCM424266.pdf>
- Valentino R, D'Esposito V, Ariemma F, Cimmino I, Beguinot F, Formisano P, 2015. Bisphenol A environmental exposure and the detrimental effects on human metabolic health: is it necessary to revise the risk assessment in vulnerable population? *J Endocrinol Invest.*, 39(3):259-63.
- Vandenberg, L.N., Hauser, R., Marcus, M., Olea, N., Welshons, W.V., 2007. Human exposure to bisphenol A (BPA). *Reprod. Toxicol.*, 24, 139–177.
- Vandenberg, L.N., Chahoud, I., Heindel, J.J., Padmanabhan, V., Paumgarten, F.J.R., Schoenfelder, G., 2010. Urinary, circulating, and tissue biomonitoring studies indicate widespread exposure to bisphenol A. *Environ Health Perspect* 118:1055–1070. doi: [10.1289/ehp.0901716](https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0901716).
- Vandenberg, L.N.; Hunt, P.A.; Myers, J.P.; Vom Saal, F.S., 2013. Human exposures to bisphenol A: Mismatches between data and assumptions. *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 28 (1), pp. 37-58.
- Vandenberg, L.N., et al., 2014. A round robin approach to the analysis of bisphenol a (BPA) in human blood samples. *Environ. Health* 13.
- Vandenberg, L. N. and Prins, G. S., 2016. Clarity in the face of confusion: new studies tip the scales on bisphenol A (BPA). *Andrology*, 4: 561-564. doi:[10.1111/andr.12219](https://doi.org/10.1111/andr.12219)
- Vernet, C., Pin, I., Giorgis-Allemand, L., Philippat, C., Benmerad, M., Quentin, J., Calafat, A. M., Ye, X., Annesi-Maesano, I., Siroux, V., Slama, R., 2017. In Utero Exposure to Select Phenols and Phthalates and Respiratory Health in Five-Year-Old Boys: A Prospective Study. *Environ Health Perspect.* 125 (9), 097006.
- Viberg H, Fredriksson A, Buratovic S, Eriksson P., 2011. Dose-dependent behavioral disturbances after a single neonatal Bisphenol A dose. *Toxicology* 290: 187-194.
- Viguié, C. et al., 2013. Maternal and fetal exposure to bisphenol A is associated with alterations of thyroid function in pregnant ewes and their newborn lambs. *Endocrinology* 154, 521–528 (2013).
- Völkel, W., Colnot, T., Csanady, G., Filser, J., Dekant, W., 2002. Metabolism and kinetics of bisphenol A in humans at low doses following oral administration. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 15, 1281–1287.
- Völkel, W., Bittner, N., Dekant, W., 2005. Quantitation of bisphenol A and bisphenol A glucuronide in biological samples by high performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 33, 1748-1757.

D5.14 - Derivation of BPA HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs)	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Eva Ougier	Page: 83

- Völkel, W., Kiranoglu, M., Fromme, H., 2008. Determination of free and total bisphenol A in human urine to assess daily uptake as a basis for a valid risk assessment. *Toxicol. Lett.* 179, 155–162.
- Völkel, W., Kiranoglu, M., Fromme, H., 2011. Determination of free and total bisphenol A in urine of infants. *Environ. Res.* 111, 143–148.
- Vom Saal, F.S. et al. 2014a. Bisphenol A (BPA) pharmacokinetics with daily oral bolus or continuous exposure via silastic capsules in pregnant rhesus monkeys: Relevance for human exposures. *Reprod. Toxicol. Elmsford* N45, 105–116.
- Vom Saal, F.S., Welshons, W.V., 2014b. Evidence that bisphenol A (BPA) can be accurately measured without contamination in human serum and urine, and that BPA causes numerous hazards from multiple routes of exposure. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.*, 398, 101–113.
- von Goetz N., Pirow R., Hart A., Bradley E., Pocas F., Arcella D., Lillegard I.T.L, Simoneau C., van Engelen J., Husoy T., Theobald A., Leclercq C., 2017. Including non-dietary sources into an exposure assessment of the European Food Safety Authority: the challenge of multi-sector chemicals such as Bisphenol A. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.*, 85 (2017), pp. 70-78.
- Wang, F., Hua, J., Chen, M.J., et al. 2012. High urinary bisphenol A concentrations in workers and possible laboratory abnormalities. *Occup Environ Med*; 69:679–84.
- Waechter, J., et al., 2007. Factors affecting the accuracy of bisphenol A and bisphenol A monoglucuronide estimates in mammalian tissues and urine samples. *Toxicol. Mech. Methods* 17 (1), 13–24.
- Wei J, Lin Y, Li Y, Ying C, Chen J, Song L, Zhou Z, Lv Z, Xia W, Chen X, Xu S., 2011. Perinatal exposure to bisphenol A at reference dose predisposes offspring to metabolic syndrome in adult rats on a high-fat diet. *Endocrinology* 152(8): 3049-3061.
- WHO (World Health Organization), 2011. Joint FAO/WHO expert meeting to review toxicological and health aspects of bisphenol A: final report, including report of stakeholder meeting on bisphenol A, 1-5 November 2010, Ottawa, Canada. Available at: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/44624/97892141564274_eng.pdf;jsessionid=66FF99150813845607437215E58148DD?sequence=1
- Xiao, G.B., Shi, J.L., He, G.H. et al., 2005. Investigation into serum BPA and sex hormone level of workers in epoxy resin manufacture. *J Environ Occup Med*; 22: 295–8.
- Xu XH, Zhang J, Wang YM, Ye YP, Luo QQ., 2010. Perinatal exposure to bisphenol-A impairs learning-memory by concomitant down-regulation of N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors of hippocampus in male offspring mice. *Hormones and Behavior* 58: 326-333.
- Xu X, Tian D, Hong X, Chen L, Xie L. 2011. Sex-specific Influence of Exposure to bisphenol-A Between Adolescence and Young Adulthood on Mouse Behaviors. *Neuropharmacology* 61: 565–573.
- Yang X, Doerge DR and Fisher JW (2013). Prediction and evaluation of route dependent dosimetry of BPA in rats at different life stages using a physiologically based pharmacokinetic model. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology* 270(1): 45-59.
- Yang X, Fisher JW, 2014. Unraveling bisphenol A pharmacokinetics using physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling. *Front Pharmacol* 5:292.
- Yang X, Doerge DR, Teeguarden JG, Fisher JW, 2015. Development of a physiologically based pharmacokinetic model for assessment of human exposure to bisphenol A. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 289(3):442–456.

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- Ye, X., et al., 2007. Temporal stability of the conjugated species of bisphenol A, parabens, and other environmental phenols in human urine. *J. Expo. Sci. Environ. Epidemiol.* 17(6), 567–572.
- Ye X, Pierik FH, Hauser R, Duty S, Angerer J, Park MM, Burdorf A, Hofman A, Jaddoe VW, Mackenbach JP, Steegers EA, Tiemeier H, Longnecker MP, 2008. Urinary metabolite concentrations of organophosphorous pesticides, bisphenol A, and phthalates among pregnant women in Rotterdam, the Netherlands: the Generation R study. *Environ Res.* 2008 Oct;108(2):260-7.
- Ye X., Zhou X, Hennings R, Kramer J, Calafat AM., 2013. Potential external contamination with bisphenol A and other ubiquitous organic environmental chemicals during biomonitoring analysis: an elusive laboratory challenge. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 121 (3), 283–286.
- Yokota H, Iwano H, Endo M, Kobayashi T, Inoue H, Ikushiro S, Yuasa A., 1999. Glucuronidation of the environmental oestrogen bisphenol A by an isoform of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase, UGT2B1, in the rat liver. *Biochemical Journal* 340, 405-409.
- Zalko, D., Jacques, C., Duplan, H., Bruel, S., Perdu, E., 2011. Viable skin efficiently absorbs and metabolises bisphenol A. *Chemosphere* 82(3):424–430, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.09.058>
- Zhou, Q., Miao, M., Ran, M., et al., 2013. Serum bisphenol-A concentration and sex hormone levels in men. *Fertil Steril*; 100: 478–82.
- Zhuang, W.L., Wu, K.S., Wang, Y.K., et al., 2015. Association of serum bisphenol-A concentration and male reproductive function among exposed workers. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol*; 68 : 38–45.